

Booklet

Experiences of Initiatives Reclaiming Territories

2025

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How to cite this document

Lukas, M., Arce, I., Mejía-Forero, K., (2025)
Experiences of Initiatives Reclaiming Territories. Booklet

2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No873082. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive Summary

The booklet "Experiences of Initiatives Reclaiming Territories" presents thirteen contributions on territorial contestation in Latin America and Europe developed in the framework of CONTESTED_TERRITORY. They grasp the involvement of diverse actors, from national states, extractivist corporations to social movements and local communities, in territorial production, as well as the myriad of practices, material and symbolic, that challenge processes of territorial accumulation and promote new ways of defending and reimagining territories.

Ranging from struggles against the commodification of natural commons and urban extractivism to the defense of natural commons and ecosystems, the contributions illustrate and privilege the various tactics, territorial praxis, initiatives and knowledge produced by local communities. As a result, this booklet highlights their active role, dislocating traditional views that prioritize state power as the main factor in territory making. Moreover, it is situated in the co-produced knowledge that seeks to displace the modern/colonial dualism between society and nature, a key separation for Western liberal understandings of the economy and knowledge.

In this context, this booklet appears in line with the objectives of CONTESTED_TERRITORY, since, through innovative comparative research to document and connect contested territories, it shows the extent to which alternative grassroots knowledge may produce practices that shape, negotiate, appropriate and collaboratively manage contested territories. It is also situated in the working packages and tasks that have thematically organized the network, namely Working Package 4: "Connecting and reclaiming Contested Territories: The scope of co-producing alternatives" and Tasks 4.2, 4.3.

Introduction

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'Contested Territories' is a research network that seeks to generate alternative knowledge by analyzing the relationships between capitalist accumulation, territorial disputes and the (de)colonial production of space. Through the concepts of 'Contested Territories' and 'Territorial Accumulation', it proposes a critical review of the connections between capital, territory and power, incorporating the knowledge and practices of local communities. These concepts have grasped the political economies that coexist in territories, as well as the dynamics of conflict and resistance that emerge in organised and everyday processes, both material and symbolic.

From the perspective of 'Contested Territories', contemporary territorial production is conceived as a dynamic process that includes insurgent practices and the appropriation of space through political, economic and epistemic contestation. This approach recognises the participation of diverse actors, from states and extractivist capital to social movements and local communities, which broadens the traditional view that privileges state power in the production of territories. In doing so, it addresses the tensions generated by contemporary economic dynamics, such as financialisation, extractivism and neoliberal narratives, that subordinate human and nonhuman life to capital accumulation.

In the midst of these dynamics, networks of resistance and alternatives emerge, reconfiguring territories through multi-scale disputes and collective processes. These resistances not only confront territorial inequalities, but also promote new forms of territorial construction that challenge hegemonic narratives and propose more inclusive and sustainable models, based on the integration of local knowledge, the recovery of community practices and the reinforcement of cultural, aesthetic, economic and epistemological alternatives.

Questioning hegemonic narratives implies approaching territorialities from diverse perspectives, given that these not only reflect the relations and needs of capital, but also represent spaces of life, resistance and alternatives, contesting and challenging capitalist accumulation and its foundations. Territorial knowledge, co-produced through the dialogue of knowledges and experiences, are configured as epistemic tools of contestation.

In this process, concepts, theories and methodologies are redefined and transformed to address the relationship between the human and nature, as well as the subject-object dualism on which the colonality of modern knowledge is based.

In this framework, Contested Territories promotes a type of research that seeks to break with traditional knowledge economies, characterised by competition, hierarchisation and disconnection between institutions and local communities. Instead, it adopts principles of reciprocity and nonhierarchical feedback to co-produce theories and methods linked to territories. This implies working closely with communities in the creation of conceptual and methodological tools that aim at reinforcing their autonomy in the production of discourses, representations and practices. This perspective positions the knowledge produced collectively by meshworks of action - territorial praxis - and imaginaries in (other) ways of knowing and inhabiting the territories.

This approach appears in the booklet "Experiences of Initiatives Reclaiming Territories", which brings together empirical research on territorial accumulation and territorial contestations in Latin America and Europe, highlighting the diversity of contesting viewpoints and methodologies that emerge in these contexts. This booklet compiles eleven experiences of territorial contestation and reappropriation that reflect a wide diversity of processes of territorial accumulation and the ways in which these are contested. These experiences range from the commodification of nature and wildlife in rural areas of the Global South to struggles against gentrification in the metropolises of the Global North. Moreover, they document a variety of tactics of resistance: legal initiatives, direct and confrontational actions, and the "stealthy" advance of alternative practices in the scales of social reproduction and everyday life.

The order of the following contributions seeks to represent the connection between socio-ecological struggles and urban contestations and co-productions, without pretending that they can be understood in isolation. On the contrary, both the practice and conceptualisation of territorial contestation are inherently relational, challenging the rigid dualities that have prevailed in social science and political action.

The *booklet* begins with the contribution of Carlos Cowan Ros. It addresses the commodification of vicuña fibre in the Central Andes by describing how its incorporation into production chains since the 19th century has generated legal and economic disputes between textile corporations and Andean communities.

While companies employ strategies such as land grabbing, greenwashing and the hybridisation of vicuñas with alpacas to maximise profits, local communities resort to legal contestation and territorial praxis based on indigenous worldviews that conceive the fibre as a common good, preserving their access to the communities. These dynamics reflect the tensions between extractivist economic models, based on the impact of the modern/colonial separation between society and nature in the subordination of natural resources to capital, and community alternatives.

Lorena Cardin's contribution focuses on ethnographic work carried out with the *Qom community Potae Napocna Navogoh* (in the *Qom* language "The claw of the anteater-The Spring") in the province of Formosa, Argentina. There it is possible to observe how, in the constant evolution of the practices of contestation to territorial accumulation processes, the communities are transformed into agents that gradually displace the hegemonic conditions imposed on the reproduction of their existence, weaving multi-scale social and geographical networks. This contribution describes the deployment of diverse strategies of territorial contestation by the *Potae Napocna Navogoh* community, which aim to recover and recognise all the hectares of their territories that are currently subordinated to the extractive logics of natural commons and rent. These protest strategies have succeeded in involving national and international sectors and diverse organisations, increasing the visibility of the conflict on different scales, multiplying direct and political action measures, and halting certain processes of territorial accumulation on the territories.

In her writing, Mónica Marión Cataño describes the territorial disputes of the Nasa people (people of water), an original people living in the southwest of Colombia. As the author points out, the struggles of the Nasa people articulate the various disputes against colonial devices, territorial dispossession and the disregard of their rights as an original people. The Regional Indigenous Council of Cauca -CRIC- is an example of territorial contestation, because it has been constituted as a platform for the defense of ancestral territories from Colombia's large landowners and, recently, the armed actors of Colombia's internal conflict. This defense is anchored to the Nasa cosmovision and the "law of origin", which is the materialization of the whole and allows defining the rights and duties in the relationship between humans and nature. The territorial disputes of the Nasa people are symbols of contestation and, simultaneously, of alternatives that coexist with the dynamics of capitalism deployed in the ancestral territories of Colombia.

In his input, Carlos Revilla describes how the territorial conflict in Alto Milluni, an indigenous community near El Alto, Bolivia, stems from the historical impacts of mining and water extractivism, which have contaminated water and soil, affecting local livelihoods.

It also highlights how water exploitation and urban expansion have intensified territorial dispossession, generating inter-communal conflicts and violence. Alto Milluni's response is founded on strengthening cohesion, identity and local resources not only to denounce and confront these threats, but also to redefine the history of exploitation and open up alternatives for collective and community wellbeing. Thus this contestation does not deny dispossession in favour of an ancestralism for tourists, but it turns the vestiges of dispossession into elements for the reconstruction and reflection of collective history. Moreover, it does not imply isolation but articulation and a broad policy of alliances in the face of multiple threats. It is not only a process of protest, mobilisation and resistance, but also of building proposals and negotiation.

Another experience from Bolivia was outlined by Fátima Zambrana, who explores livelihood strategies as forms of daily contestation in the face of poverty and inequality in the Metropolitan Region of Cochabamba. These strategies, developed by individuals and communities, include self-management of basic resources, community organisation and solidarity networks that challenge dynamics of territorial exclusion and unequal accumulation. In the face of historical and contemporary processes that perpetuate segregation and marginalisation, these practices demonstrate the resilience of vulnerable populations and their active role in the reconfiguration of fragmented territories, transforming them into spaces of resistance and social adaptation.

From Ecuador, Manuel Bayón presents the case of oil extractivism in the Ecuadorian Amazon as an emblematic example of capitalist territorial accumulation, underscoring its environmental, social and economic impacts. He describes how this activity has polluted water sources and affected indigenous and peasant communities, while the benefits are concentrated in importing countries and national elites. The relationship between territorial accumulation and its contestation has led to three reflections around the agency of affected local communities. Firstly, it is possible to curb corporate power through broad alliances of national peasant, indigenous and urban sectors. Second, the relevance of the provision of basic services demanded by the populations that have been attacked for decades by oil exploitation, and which can only be provided at present by the states themselves. Finally, since the victory of the Yasuní referendum, alliances beyond the local conflicts themselves are possible, forging transnational and transregional lines of political action. The union of popular urban sectors and communities around common axes in the face of environmental devastation and capitalist elites allows for visualizing political alliances that go beyond the conventional scales of anti-extractive struggles and to re-imagine post-extractive futures.

From Chile, the contribution by Ana Laura Galarza delves into the case of the expansion of the port in the coastal city of San Antonio, located in the region of Valparaíso. Her input addresses the diverse repertoires of socio-cultural, patrimonial and artistic practices or lines of action, and interprets them from the theoretical frameworks of insurgent planning and the artistic practices of expanded mediation (PAMEX). As a result, the investigative activities are situated within the territories, not outside or on them. The fate of the mega-project in San Antonio has been determined by scientific and normative contestation initiatives driven by inhabitants, organisations and social movements, which focus on the formal protection of the ecosystems of the Ojos de Mar wetland and the mouth of the Maipo River from the mega-construction plans of the Empresa Portuaria San Antonio. Nevertheless, as the author argues, this focus on the normative and scientific dimensions of the socio-environmental conflict in San Antonio tends to make invisible the counter-narratives, networks of practices or 'seeds towards the decolonisation of the imagination' (patrimonial, socio-cultural, artistic and eco-sensorial) of insurgent planning that communities, including the author of this contribution, have co-produced, to foster the link with the territories in a multidimensional way and to protect the ecosystems of San Antonio.

Another Chilean case is presented by Ignacio Arce and Michael Lukas. It discusses the conflict around the Colina River, in the commune of the same name, north of Santiago, where a local organisation is developing practices of re-appropriation of this environment, seeking to have it declared a Protected Wildlife Area. This declaration is related to the impacts of the overlapping of mining, agro-industrial and real estate extractivism, which has been conceptualized as "peri-urban extractivism". The case describes the territorial context that led to the expansion of peri-urban extractivism in the area and how the conflict is an instance to redefine spaces that have been privatised and appropriated by capital, to propose other ways of conceiving territoriality and care for the different forms of life that exist there.

In his contribution, Roberto Busnelli describes from the other side of the Andes the experience of the School of Habitat and Sustainability of the National University of San Martín, Argentina, in carrying out collective construction and urban co-evaluation workshops aimed at integrating academic training with the resolution of territorial problems in vulnerable neighbourhoods of Buenos Aires. Through participatory practices, such as collaborative surveys, audited walks and joint design with the communities, the project seeks to transform public space and improve the quality of habitat through architectural proposals that respond to local needs, promoting social cohesion and reinforcing the role of architecture as a tool for territorial justice.

Gabriel Silvestre and co-authors grasp how social movements in Latin American cities, such as Rosario, Belo Horizonte and Santiago, have responded to territorial conflicts caused by urban extractivism, community displacement and real estate speculation. These movements, such as 'Ciudad Futura', 'Brigadas Populares' and 'Ukamau', have implemented dual strategies that combine the occupation of institutional spaces with practical actions: land occupation, co-creation of social housing projects and political pressure. The combination of strategies have tackled displacement and promoted social rights. Confronted with historical processes of territorial accumulation and urban inequality, these initiatives have generated new forms of resistance, producing inclusive and sustainable alternatives for territorial development that have inspired both local and global action.

From Spain, Héctor Grad's contribution analyses the San Fernando Market in Lavapiés, Madrid, as an example of the agency of self-organised producers and consumers in the configuration of alternative solidarity circuits of production-commercialisation-consumption in food markets. Food markets are contested territories in the face of processes of gentrification and touristification, in which markets are spaces captured by the neoliberal logics of urban rent maximisation. Grad highlights how alternative practices, such as consumer groups and agro-ecological initiatives, turn the market into an urban common, challenging the logic of capitalism and reclaiming traditional community and social functions, even in hostile contexts of neoliberal territorial accumulation.

Alejandro Armas-Díaz's entry exposes the processes of commodification of common goods and territorial conflicts produced in the different stages of tourism exploitation in the Canary Islands, territories that, historically, have been located in the periphery of Europe. As Armas-Díaz points out, the expansion of tourism in the archipelago has been possible due to the continuity of the colonial project initiated in the 15th century and Franco's dictatorship, where an agenda towards capitalist accumulation based on the privatization of land and tourist exploitation has been imposed. Hence, in the archipelago of the Canary Islands, tourist activity is configured as a manifestation of postcolonial territorialization, whose representations are related to insularity and the exoticization of nature. Despite the intensity of the different stages of the historical-territorial expansion of tourism, they have been challenged by initiatives of territorial defense and popular mobilization, combining protest, legislative interventions and the creation of collective alternatives.

Finally, Pablo Ruiz's contribution presents the 'Tenant Survey', an instrument developed by the different organisations of 'Contested Territories' together with social movements and tenants' unions in Barcelona, Madrid, Lisbon, Buenos Aires, Karlsruhe, Leipzig, Manchester and Santiago de Chile. The survey responds to the conflicts unleashed by the local and global financial crises that dramatically affected the housing market, deepening the trend towards rental housing and the concentration of home ownership titles in large landlords and investment funds. In this context, the 'Tenant Survey' appears as a tool of contestation, as it allows, through participatory methods, to document structural inequalities in the housing market with neighbourhood communities, to notice the power relations that underlie the supply and demand of rental housing, to situate data collection processes in the specific needs of the territories and, as a result, to strengthen the strategies of contestation of communities in the face of rental housing markets. As this contribution shows, the survey has fuelled debates and mobilisations related to fair access to housing in the contexts in which it has been applied. It has also made it possible to propose alternatives that guarantee the right to housing, challenging the hegemony of the tenant model.

By showing the aforementioned eleven cases this booklet goes beyond documenting territorial struggles and their strategies of contestation. It seeks to demonstrate contestation not only as resisting processes of territorial accumulation, but also as transformative processes of the relations between subjects and territories, questioning the dominant categories that have historically separated communities from their living spaces or habitats. This implies understanding the multiple ways in which territories are experienced and recreated, appropriated and contested in a context of advancing and expanding frontiers of capitalisation and appropriation. Each contribution should not be understood in isolation, but as part of a web of diverse experiences that dialogue and question each other, making it possible to draw connections between different contexts and forms of territorial dispute. By articulating cases from Latin America and Europe, this booklet seeks to advance a broader and more relational understanding of current territorial conflicts, offering perspectives and methodologies that strengthen both critical research and action in defence of territories and the construction of other futures.

Figure representing the different nodes that contributed to the booklet, as well as the locations where the experiences come from.

"Territorial knowledge, co-produced through dialogue, becomes an epistemic tool contesting capitalist accumulation and its foundations."

Experiences Reclaiming Territories

The Vicuña as an Object of Dispute: Capitalist and Community Logics in the Conservation and Use of a Common Good

Cowan Ros, Carlos
CEUR/CONICET - Argentina

In this case, the disputes surrounding the "conservation and sustainable use" of the vicuña are analysed. The vicuña (*Vicugna vicugna*) is a wild species belonging to the South American camelid group, which until recently was in danger of extinction. It inhabits the Puna and High Andean biogeographical areas of Peru, Bolivia, Argentina and Chile, in the large region of the Central Andes. Vicuña fibre is distinguished by its exceptional fineness, lightness and softness, and is the most highly valued natural fibre of animal origin on the market and the one that generates the greatest added value.

The value chain of this fibre connects, on the one hand, members of Andean indigenous-peasant communities who harvest the fibre using ancestral techniques and, on the other hand, the most economically powerful elites in the world. A small number of textile corporations, which specialise in luxury brands, control all the value-adding links to the fibre, which are located outside the vicuña territory.

[1] In November 2024, a vicuña jacket fetched 27,500 Euros on the European market <https://es.loropiana.com/en/p/man/outerwear-jackets/tov-parka-FAN2089> (access: 27/11/2024).

In recent decades, the economic exploitation of the vicuña has become an object of dispute in the Central Andes vis-à-vis the conditions and definitions for the conservation of this species. This section analyses the configuration and evolution of the conflict around the vicuña and the fields in which the struggles take place, the normative and the economic, focusing on the actions deployed by members of Andean peasant communities.

In the second half of the 19th century, a value chain was built around vicuña fibre, driven by European haute couture shops (Enciso, 2007). The incessant increase in the prestige and value of vicuña garments triggered indiscriminate hunting. At the end of the 1960s, faced with the imminent extinction of the species, international and national regulatory frameworks prohibited the hunting, collection, use and commercialisation of vicuñas and their derivatives. As a result, the vicuña was banned as a commodity and as an exchange commodity and, consequently, removed from the universe of legal commodities (Cowan Ros, 2022).

Andean inhabitants of Jujuy province, Argentina, herding wild vicuñas in a chaku.

In the 1980s, in view of the sustained recovery of the species, the "sustainable use" of the fibre for commercial purposes was gradually authorised (Acebes et al. 2018). The reintroduction of vicuña fibre as a legal commodity mobilised the attention of different actors (textile corporations, indigenous-peasant communities, state institutions, environmental activists, etc.), initiating the rearticulation of the value chain around vicuña fibre, which also brought into play different interests and economic logics, around which disputes and conflicts became dynamic.

In the regulatory field, between 1969 and the end of the 20th century, a system of regulation at multiple levels of government (supranational, national and subnational) was produced for the "conservation" and "sustainable use" of the species. Two production models came into conflict: captive breeding of the species and feral management. The first model converges with the capitalist logic of production, seeking to control productive factors in order to provide greater productive predictability and maximise profits. From the perspective of environmentalists, captivity, by domesticating the species, strips it of one of its fundamental qualities: wildness.

The model of management in silvetry preserves this last characteristic, and through live shearing with subsequent release of the animals, makes the conservation of the species compatible with the generation of additional income for the Andean indigenous-peasant communities. Initially, the first management model was designed and sponsored by an Argentinean state agency for science and technology, and the second by the German cooperation agency. In the 1980s, both models spread throughout the countries with vicuña presence and a heterogeneity of conflicts unfolded at different levels and scales.

The position that managed to prevail is reflected in the first article of the "Agreement for the

“The reintroduction of vicuña fibre as a legal commodity mobilised the attention of different actors”

Andean villagers shearing wild vicuñas in a chaku, Jujuy province, Argentina.

Conservation and Use of the Vicuña” (1979), the main treaty regulating the use of the species, which states that "the conservation of the vicuña constitutes an alternative economic production for the benefit of the Andean population and commits to its gradual use under strict State control, applying techniques under the management of wild fauna" (CCMV, 1979). In the national regulations, the vicuña persisted as a public good, under the guardianship of the State, not susceptible to privatisation. The fibre is only privatised when the State grants the right to shear.

The consecration of this perspective of exploitation is the result of an environmental struggle. Far from becoming a contentious practice in the streets, the dispute took place in bureaucratic spheres (state agencies, international environmental conservation organisations, multilateral bodies, the scientific sphere, etc.) due to the practices of biologists, public officials and environmentalists interested in making the conservation of the species compatible with the benefit of the peasant-indigenous populations of the "vicuña territory". This posed obstacles to the intervention of textile corporations in the first link of the value chain: obtaining vicuña fibre.

As previously mentioned, a small group of textile corporations control the purchase and value addition of vicuña fibre (spinning, weaving and garment manufacturing), which is a production process carried out outside the vicuña territory and the American continent. These corporations have managed to appropriate around 95% of the value generated along the fibre value chain, with the remaining value in the hands of the members of the indigenous-peasant communities.

Despite the capacity of the textile corporations to generate and appropriate value in most of the links in the vicuña chain, they have deployed different practices to circumvent the regulatory framework and control the first link of the chain to guarantee the supply of fibre and increase their capacity to appropriate value.

The practices implemented by textile corporation and related state agents have been (i) the purchase of large extensions of land with vicuña presence in the Andean zone -land grabbing- to activate the category "Andean settlers";

Andean villagers enclosing wild vicuñas in a corral during a *chaku*, Jujuy province, Argentina.

(ii) the creation of reserves for the conservation of vicuñas in areas of high vicuña density with the authorisation of governments -*greenwashing*-; (iii) the creation of the *paco-vicuña*, a hybrid between vicuña and alpaca, in order to extract the new specimen from the normative framework of the vicuña and produce without conditions; (iv) and the association and implementation of "cooperation projects with vicuña producers". Regarding these initiatives, those who strive to ensure that the economic exploitation of vicuñas benefits the Andean people have lodged complaints and worked through intermediaries (representatives in the agreements, legislators, etc.) to reinforce the regulatory framework or reverse the progress made by the corporations.

The phenomenon described around vicuña fibre is interpreted as part of the process of *neoliberalisation of nature*, understood as the expansion and deepening of the commodification of (new) natural goods *vis-à-vis* the creation of compatible regulatory frameworks. This phenomenon is a fundamental logic of production and regulation to overcome the capitalist and even environmental crisis (McCarthy & Prudham 2004; Smith 2007; Igoe & Brockington 2007 and Castree 2008).

Although the commodification of vicuña fibre, as well as the deregulation and reregulation of the normative framework for its conservation and exploitation, can be observed, there are also some limits to the penetration of capitalist relations of production over this natural resource. For example, the persistence of the vicuña as a public good, i.e. not susceptible to privatisation, and the prioritisation of the granting of fibre extraction rights to Andean settlers are limits that textile corporations face and seek to circumvent.

These "limits" arise from the actions of environmental activists in different spheres of normative production and at different scales. They are interpreted as practices of creative resistance, through which they seek to regulate the economic exploitation of the species in favour of Andean inhabitants, limiting the incursion and capacity for appropriation of the value generated around vicuña fibre by external economic agents.

The members of the peasant-indigenous communities, with the support of state agents and NGOs, have deployed associative, intra- and inter-community modalities for obtaining, adding value through handicrafts (making yarn, fabrics and garments) and marketing vicuña fibre. In this way, they pursue a new source of income for their domestic economies and to challenge the textile corporations in the generation and appropriation of value generated around vicuña fibre, striving for greater permanence and circulation in the vicuña territory.

Community management of vicuña in the wild is a new economic activity compatible with the conservation of the species in its wild condition. It is also compatible with their economic strategies, as it is suitable for multiple activities and does not compete with other activities for resources (land, water or labour). Among the members of indigenous communities, vicuñas are perceived as a common good, like other material goods (water, pastures, halls, roads, irrigation ditches, etc.) and symbolic goods (festivals, etc.). Their maintenance is carried out according to the collective interest and with responsibility, for which they contribute collective labour.

A distinctive aspect of the incorporation of vicuña fibre production in Andean communities is that this new activity has revived an ancestral indigenous logic: collectivisation of production, partly favoured by the management model in silvestry, which is the only economic activity carried out in this way (Cowan Ros, 2019). Here we observe how indigenous-peasant communities mobilise representations and practices specific to their culture in the implementation of modes of production of a natural good to make conservation compatible with its use, disputing the generation and appropriation of the value generated by international textile corporations.

Although the members of the peasant-indigenous communities receive a significant contribution through the production of vicuña fibre, they are only able to maintain their productive enterprises with state support, due to the infrastructure and management costs involved. In recent years, they have begun a process of adding value to their handicrafts (spinning and weaving), but low productivity and lack of technical knowledge limit their economic profitability.

Given the sophistication and high cost of machinery, adding value through industrial technology is economically impracticable without state support. In recent years, members of indigenous communities have organised, mobilised and joined forces with environmentalists to actively participate in national and international forums to regulate the conservation and use of vicuñas, in order to emerge as an economic actor with specific interests and needs, disputing the *lobby* of the textile corporations. They understand that the dispute in the economic field can only be successful if it is correlated with the field of regulation, as this is where the conditions for the success of the different production models are established.

In conclusion, although a regulatory framework has been created around the use of vicuña fibre that seeks to benefit the Andean population, it has not been possible to avoid the re-edition of a model of extractivist accumulation (Svampa, 2015) around another highly valued natural resource in the Andean region of South America.

Wild vicuñas enclosed during a chaku, Jujuy province, Argentina.

“In recent years, they have begun a process of adding value to their handicrafts (spinning and weaving), but low productivity and lack of technical knowledge limit their economic profitability”

However, the practices of creative resistance produced by indigenous-peasant communities stand out, which are based on recovering their cultural references, fundamentally communalisation, and adapting them to the design of a production model compatible with the conservation of the species in its wild condition and with their production systems. In the same vein, it is important to highlight the simultaneous struggle in the economic and normative fields, on multiple scales, which the communities are waging to challenge textile corporations for the appropriation of the value generated around vicuña fibre, seeking to prevent the emergence of a new model of extractivist accumulation around a resource of interest to the Andean area, as it happened with lithium and other minerals.

References

Castree, Noel. 2008. "Neoliberalising Nature: The Logics of Deregulation and Reregulation". *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 40:131-152. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a3999>

Convenio para la Conservación y Manejo de la Vicuña. 1979. Disponible en: <http://www.saij.gob.ar/23582-nacional-convenio-para-conservacion-manejo-vicuna-Int0003476-1988-07-20/123456789-0abc-defg-g67-43000tcanyel>

Cowan Ros, C. 2019. Community management of vicuñas in silvestría as management of a common good in Yavi, *Brazilian Journal of Development* 5 (7):9705-9732, DOI:10.34117/bjdv5n7-148.

Cowan Ros, C.; Marcos, M. F. and Muro, M. (2022) "Las vicuñas como problema de gobierno. Gubernamentalidad ambiental a múltiples niveles y disputas por el modelo de aprovechamiento de la especie", in *Revista Brasileira de Estudos Urbanos e Regionais (RBEUR)*, Place: São Paulo; Year: 2022.

Igoe, Jim and Brockington, Dan. 2007. "Neoliberal conservation: a brief introduction". *Conservation and Society* 5 (4) 432-449. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26392898>

McCarthy, James and Prudham, Scott. 2004. "Neoliberal nature and the nature of neoliberalism". *Geoforum* 35: 275-283. DOI:[10.1016/J.GEOFORUM.2003.07.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOFORUM.2003.07.003)

Smith, Neil. 2007. "Nature as accumulation strategy". *Socialist Register*. 43:16-36.

Svampa, Maristella. 2015: Development in question? Some coordinates of the Latin American debate. In: Svampa (coord.) *El desarrollo en disputa. Actores, conflictos y modelos de desarrollo en la Argentina contemporáneas*. Buenos Aires: Ediciones UNGS. Pp. 21-38.

Community Assembly. Photography: Courtesy of the qom Potae Napocna Navogoh Community

The Struggle for the Recovery of the Territory of the Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh Community (Formosa, Argentina)

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This paper seeks to make visible the strategies deployed by the indigenous Qom people of the Qom community *Potae Napocna Navogoh* (in the Qom language "The claw of the anteater-The Spring") in the province of Formosa, Argentina. This analysis is based on the ethnographic fieldwork that I have been carrying out with the community since 2001.

The struggle of the community has become a paradigmatic case of territorial contestation due to its national scope; the wide visibility it acquired; its strong level of physical and political confrontation; the social meanings it managed to mobilise; the forcefulness of the measures adopted by the indigenous people; and the number of social actors and personalities involved: national and provincial government, indigenous movement, Supreme Court of Justice of the Nation (CSJN), National Administration of National Parks (APN), National University of Formosa (UNAF), Human Rights NGOs (Amnesty International, Servicio Paz y Justicia, Madres de Plaza de Mayo Línea Fundadora, Asamblea Permanente por los Derechos Humanos, Centro de Estudios Legales y Sociales, among others).

In order to analyse the complex articulation between structural constraints and Qom agency, I will take Lawrence Grossberg's (1992) cartographic metaphor, which refers to the capacity of hegemony to enable certain social and geographical spaces through which subjects must move within the framework of structured mobility. In particular, I am interested in analysing how the indigenous Qom, due to their trajectory of aboriginality (Ramos, 2005), became agents with the capacity to contest these subjections, moving towards new social and geographical spaces linked to the national and international spheres.

Since the process of conquest and colonisation, the indigenous peoples of the Chaco region have been separated from the control of the material conditions of their productive activities (hunting, gathering and fishing) and induced into seasonal wage labour and commercial agricultural activity, especially cotton cultivation in the case of the Qom of eastern Formosa (Trincherro, 2000). However, the oscillation of cotton cultivation in terms of surface area and the sown volume,

as well as the mechanisation process and technological development linked to cotton, led to a decrease in the hiring of indigenous labour as harvesters. At the same time, the concentration and centralisation of capital in cotton production around 1960 affected the possibility for indigenous people to continue to develop as independent commercial producers (Iñigo Carrera, 2008). Currently, most of the province's indigenous population subsists mainly on social programmes distributed by both governments. In some cases, they manage to supplement this income by combining certain economic strategies such as the sale of handicrafts and hunting products; temporary work for criollos; public employment and even the leasing of their lands. As Iñigo Carrera (2008) argues, capital has prevented them from developing their capacity as productive subjects, assigning them the status of surplus working population.

Potae Napocna Navogoh is a rural indigenous community located in the northeast of the province, 174 kilometres from the city of Formosa, in the border area with the Republic of Paraguay. It has the most fertile lands in the province, and its landscape is formed by bushes, marshes and lagoons. Based on the census prepared for the elections that took place in 2011, it is estimated that 4000 indigenous Qom people live in the community.

The territorial claim dates back to 1930, when the community proposed to cacique Trifón Sanabria that he travel to Buenos Aires to request recognition of their territory.² However, in response, in 1940 the national state signed a decree recognising only 5,000 hectares of their territory. Although their traditional territory is substantially larger, the community title, which was granted to them by the province in 1985, recognised 5,187 hectares.

Community protest march in downtown Buenos Aires. Photography: courtesy of the Qom *Potae Napocna Navogoh* community.

It should be clarified that the Qom claims 26,000 hectares, most of which are in the hands of the Río Pilcomayo National Park. However, indigenous claims to recover their territory have had to confront the Formosan and national development model of exploitation of the natural commons, together with the value of the community's lands.

The most tense moment in the confrontation for the recovery of the territory took place in 2010 when the community led by the *qarashe* (leader) Félix Diaz (Lazzari and Cardin, 2013) blocked the national route 86 for four months in order to prevent the construction of a UNAF headquarters within their territory.

The provincial government was trying to carry out this construction without consultation. In response to the indigenous measure, on 23 November 2010, the provincial police in coordination with the national gendarmerie violently repressed the demonstrators, resulting in two deaths, beatings, the burning of Qom houses and the arrest of elderly people and children. The community, through a request for a precautionary measure, managed to stop the construction work. Later, they filed an appeal for legal protection of their land claim, which has been before the CSJN since 2011, awaiting a ruling.

Given that the aggression towards the community continued after the repression, the community requested, and obtained, an international precautionary measure from the IACHR to demand that the Argentine State adopt the necessary measures to guarantee the life and physical integrity of the members of the community against harassment by the provincial police.

“Most of the province's indigenous population subsists mainly on social programmes distributed by both governments”.

[2] Traditional territory is considered to be the maximum space that a People has ever occupied in the past (Surrallés, 2009).

Community roadblock (2010). Photography: courtesy of the Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh community.

In 2011, Félix Díaz, together with members of the community who had travelled to the city of Buenos Aires to make their claim visible, developed a series of political action measures: marches to the National Congress and the Government House; dissemination of the problem in national and international media; participation in press conferences; cutting and installation of a camp in the centre of the city and the decision to hold a hunger strike.

As a result of this political action, the community managed to get both national and local governments to participate in a dialogue with the aim of resolving the conflict. This is an unprecedented case in Argentina, since the governments never agree to dialogue with social actors who are taking measures of force. Undoubtedly, the national government, led by Cristina Fernández de Kirchner, at that time needed to deactivate the conflict that gained great visibility and support from many sectors of society. However, the same national government soon decided to ignore the Qom claim, prioritising its political alliance with the governor of the province of Formosa, Gildo Insfrán.

The CSJN, after holding a public hearing with all the actors involved (Cardin 2013), ordered the national government to carry out the territorial survey required by national law No. 26,160 in the province of Formosa. Unfortunately, after four months of work, the result of the survey was disappointing for the community, because the maps that were drawn up showed

a smaller area than the one that appears in their 1985 title and, consequently, the Qom did not accept these results (Cardin, 2018 and 2019). They decided, therefore, to present to the CSJN the map that I produced together with them in the framework of the participatory mapping activities that we developed over a decade of joint work. Some of the maps we produced during this process have been incorporated into the ATLAS of the *Contested Territories* network.

Although the CSJN has not yet ruled on the territorial claim, the following achievements of the Qom territorial protest can be considered: halted the university project; forced the national government to register it in the National Register of Indigenous Communities (RENACI); obtained strong support from many sectors of the citizenry as a result of the alliances they forged; made the territorial conflict visible at the national and international level; and, above all, achieved recognition as subjects with the right to be consulted on matters that concern them.

In short, the *Qom Potae Napocna Navogoh* community has become a paradigmatic case of indigenous agency, having confronted, like David against Goliath, the process of territorial accumulation carried out by both governments, with minimal material resources but with solid symbolic and political resources.

[3] In December 2024, the President of the Nation, Javier Milei, repealed the national law 26.160, which provided for territorial surveys of indigenous communities, established the territorial emergency and suspended the evictions of indigenous communities with territorial conflicts.

[4] <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/potae-napocna-navogoh/>

References

- Cardin, L. 2013. "Construcciones en disputa de la identidad qom. La escenificación de las diferencias ante la Corte Suprema de Justicia de la Nación". In Tola F., Medrano C. and Cardin L. (eds.), Gran Chaco. Ontologías, poder, afectividad. City of Buenos Aires, Rumbo Sur.
<https://rid.unrn.edu.ar/jspui/handle/20.500.12049/2486>
- Cardin, L. 2018. "Entre realidades y simulacros. El proceso de relevamiento del territorio qom". In M. Carrasco (ed.) Campos de interlocución y políticas de reconocimiento indígena en Argentina. Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, Antropofagia. ISBN 978-987-1983-37-7. <https://rid.>
- Cardin, L. 2019. "Territorial survey of Indigenous Peoples. Risks and challenges". In S. Guiñazú (ed.) Dossier La Ley 26.160: Una herramienta en defensa de las territorialidades. Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires, Revista Papeles de Trabajo UNSAM, (13/23). pp. 30-49.
<https://revistasacademicas.unsam.edu.ar/index.php/papdetrab/issue/view/49>
- Grossberg, L. 1992. We Gotta Get Out of This Place. Popular Conservatism and Postmodern Culture. New York, Routledge.
- Iñigo Carrera, V. 2008. "Sujetos productivos, sujetos políticos, sujetos indígenas: las formas de su objetivación mercantil entre los tobas del este de Formosa", doctoral thesis, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires.
- Lazzari A. and Cardin L. 2013. "¿Quién le teme a Félix Díaz?" Anfibia, Revista de la Universidad Nacional de San Martín, (digital publication)
- Ramos, A. 2005 "Trayectorias de Aboriginalidad en las comunidades mapuche del Noroeste de Chubut (1990-2003)". PhD thesis, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras.
<http://repositorio.filo.uba.ar/handle/filodigital/1263>
- Surrallés, A. 2009. "Entre derecho y realidad. Antropología y territorios amazónicos en un futuro próximo". Bulletin de l'IFEA, 29-45.

Resistance for Survival of the Nasa People in Colombia

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The Nasa people, people of water, is one of the 115 original peoples of Colombia. It is made up of indigenous fighters, who live in the southwest of Colombia, especially in the department of Cauca, where 88.6% of the population resides, equivalent to about 165,000 people. The Nasa speak their own language, Nasa Yuwe, and are governed by their law of origin, their own law and their cosmovision practices.

His trajectory of struggle dates back to colonial times in which one of the main chiefs, Juan Tama, achieved the recognition of the native peoples by the Crown: The chiefdom of Toribio, in the north of the Cauca; the chiefdom of Pitayó, in the center with the populations of Pitayó, Jambaló, Caldono, Quichaya; the chiefdom of Togoima, in the south of Tierradentro and the chiefdom of Vitoncó, in the north of Tierradentro.

With this achievement, Juan Tama continued his political work within his community achieving the unification of Paez, as the Nasa territory was previously called, against the ambitions of the Spanish domination and left as a legacy the law of origin for the strengthening of his people and thus achieve the survival as an indigenous people, a mission that has been continued by leaders such as Quintin Lame, Álvaro Ulcué Chocué and indigenous organizations constituted for the defense of the peoples such as the Regional Indigenous Council of Cauca- CRIC, therefore, the political struggle of the Nasa indigenous people has deep roots that are intertwined with the history of colonization, territorial dispossession and the search for recognition of their rights.

Since the arrival of the colonizers, indigenous peoples have faced the loss of their lands and resources, which has led to a constant resistance to recover and protect their ancestral territory, the struggle for autonomy, the defense of their cosmovision and the vindication of political and social rights.

The CRIC's platform of struggle has 10 points of which seven are related to the territorial struggle:

Minga; Photography: Cristian Tafur

"The Nasa people resist to recover their ancestral territory, defend autonomy, and protect Mother Earth."

- 1) Recover the land of the resguardos and carry out the defense of the ancestral territory and living spaces of the indigenous communities,
- 2) Expand the resguardos,
- 3) Strengthen the Indigenous councils,
- 4) Do not pay terraje ,
- 5) Make known the laws on indigenous people and demand their fair application,
- 6) Defend the history, language and indigenous customs and
- 7) Recover, Defend, Protect the living spaces in harmony and balance with Mother Earth.

In the Nasa worldview, spirituality is linked to reason, which is why the indigenous people maintain that "they think with the heart" (Peña, 2015). Life takes place on the physical plane, but the underground, where the bodies of those who have departed and are in the spiritual plane guiding the people, are also part of the cosmovision.

Uma kiwe is everything, she is the mother earth that provides what is necessary for the existence of the Nasa being. With mother earth one achieves food autonomy, one learns, and in her is what is required to live in harmony: nature, water, plants, animals, the human and the non-human as elements in the cosmivision. The walas/traditional doctors or elders are in charge of guiding the people, taking care of them and protecting them with the guidance of the spirits; they are the wise men who make payments and perform rituals of gratitude to mother earth to achieve harmonized territories. For the indigenous people, the territories in conflict are disharmonized territories that do not comply with the mandates of Juan Tama and disregard the law of origin.

The struggles of Nasa people

One of the most acute territorial conflicts in the history of the Nasa people has been over Mother Earth, and the desire for power by settlers/landowners in their quest for wealth. The indigenous people have been dispossessed of their appropriated lands through strategies such as slavery, payment of terraje and some of them were confined to the mountainous areas as an alternative to protect and safeguard life. The resguardos were the way to grant physical place to the indigenous people, as it appears in the title of Law 89 of 1890, "sometimes the difficulties were derived from the reduced size of the resguardos...the portion that corresponded to each indigenous person was so small, that no use could be made of it" (Ariza, 2009, p.153).

The struggle of the Nasa indigenous peoples has been tainted by the assassination of leaders who defend their territories against the economic interests of extractive companies, drug trafficking and the violence of armed groups. Leaders are seen as obstacles to the advancement of projects that threaten their lands and livelihoods, which makes them targets of attacks. Stigmatization and criminalization of their struggle are factors of violence in Colombia, so that ancestral territories have been the scene of the Colombian armed conflict, historical violence has affected the indigenous and peasant population and the land has suffered the wounds of a war that gives no truce.

The historical presence of the insurgency in the department of Cauca, the assassinations of social leaders, the massacres that have occurred and the geopolitical importance of the Cauca River as a strategic corridor for the circulation of arms and drugs, accentuate the conflicts in the ancestral territories.

Map of Cauca. Cartography of violence made from used bullet casings. Artwork by Edison Quiñones, National Center for Historical Memory

In the national context, the 1991 Constitution split in two the paths of the insurgency: those who made it a peace treaty and entered into political life and those who considered it insufficient or ineffective to address the major social problems of the country; and the Law of Victims and Land Restitution of 2011, which recognizes the horrors of war and the thousands of people affected by it and the need to address one of the most critical issues of the conflict, which is undoubtedly that of land (Sanchez, 2021. P. 25).

Prior to the peace process, from 1991 to 2016, the armed conflict in the Nasa's ancestral territories was characterized by the presence of guerrilla groups, paramilitaries and the army, which generated an environment of violence and forced displacement. Indigenous communities were caught in the middle of this conflict, suffering human rights violations and facing the militarization of their territories.

With the signing of the peace agreements in 2016, a decrease in violence was expected, but the reality has been complex. Despite progress, the conflict has not ended and indigenous leaders continue to be killed. The Nasa people are governed by the Law of Origin; however, as their reservations are territorially located in areas delimited by the national territorial ordinance, there is an overlap between the actions of one law and the other.

One of the leaders defines the law of origin as "the principle of these beings that we call ourselves Nasa, it is the rigorousness of the natural norms that exist in mother earth, in the territory and in all the spaces of life.

The law of origin is the materialization of the whole, us, the so-called humans, the animals, mother nature; The trees, the rain, the rivers, for me that conjugation of good living and the natural order that allows us to define some rules, duties and rights to be able to make an exercise of coexistence beyond the natural human, a permanent interaction and relationship of man with nature, because just as nature gives us, we have the obligation to sustain what she gives us, without nature and the elements that are there is not possible the existence and life in this house that is called planet or universe; the law of origin is not only the norms that are possibly also codified in nature, but the combination of spirituality to understand and comprehend how we should behave in order to have what today we call the good living, which we have always said that it is the *wet wet fxizenxi*" (F. Valencia).

"The 2016 peace agreements brought progress, but violence persists, and indigenous leaders are still killed."

The conflict is intensifying

In recent years, we have seen how the residual organized armed groups and dissidents of the former FARC have reorganized in the face of non-compliance with the peace agreements and the polarization of a divided citizenry. In addition to the internal situation and disregard for differences, there is the presence of other actors in the conflict, such as criminal gangs, drug traffickers, and reorganized groups that see the ancestral territories as an opportunity to plant illicit crops, which has led to an intensification of the conflict and the dispute for control over land tenure and use.

According to the National Indigenous Organization of Colombia, ONIC, at least 58,000 indigenous people were victims of the conflict in 2023. Of these, 23,570 inhabitants of different ethnic groups were affected by the confinements - curfews imposed by the armed groups - and 3,022 suffered different types of attacks. In addition, 634 were threatened and 45 killed in the context of Colombia's armed conflict.

The territorial control that some indigenous leaders of the self-government manage to exercise in their territories with the support of the indigenous guard

and through negotiation with the armed actors, is altered by the voluntary and forced recruitment of young people by armed groups in the resguardos. The situation is increasingly critical, as a leader of the Pueblo Nuevo resguardo narrates,

"the new generations of young people are unaware of the political struggles that our elders have fought to defend the territory and are attracted by telephones and what they see on them, not being able to access opportunities, they are seduced by members of armed groups who promise them money, power and weapons or what is worse, they take them by force and without family consent" (leader of Pueblo Nuevo, 2024).

"They are taking our children away from us, just as they are awakening to life", (leader of Pick we tha fiw reservation, 2025).

The Human Rights Observatory of INDEPAZ, reveals that indigenous children have not been left out of this terrible situation. The Association of Indigenous Cabildos of Northern Cauca reported that, between January 2017 and April 2024, 817 indigenous minors from northern Cauca, were recruited by armed groups with the objective of training them for war as well as for surveillance and intelligence gathering actions, which reflects the persistence of violence and the lack of guarantees for security in ancestral territories, despite the efforts of the cabildos to protect and maintain their living spaces with the support of community processes.

For the indigenous people, the exercise of their own rights is defined as "the superior rules, the things that cannot be touched, that cannot be moved and that, if they are moved, cause an imbalance in our lives and in nature, for example, to take care of and protect the mother earth is a major right, that regardless of the people we are, we have to do it because that is the essence of indigenous life. A major right is our mother tongue, to transmit it, teach it, maintain it, revitalize it, recreate it, it is an immovable for us; community life is a major right; it is what each one of us, men, women, children and old people have to know to respect them and not transgress them because it would be putting our existence at risk" (F. Valencia, 2019), thus, the life of the indigenous people is permanently at risk as they feel that their territories become scenarios of pain, dispute, control and territorial possession for economic, political purposes, spaces that become "landscapes of fear", the opposite of the Nasa cosmovision.

Ritual of the Saakhelu, of gratitude to Mother Earth. Huellas Resguardo, Cauca. Photography: Alejandra Legarda

Actors and Response Practices

"To speak Nasa Yuwe is to defend the territory".

(Indigenous leader, 2022)

The Nasa indigenous people are a symbol of political resistance in the country, their practices in Minga, their example of solidarity, their firmness in the face of situations and conflicts that they live permanently in their territories have positioned them as warriors and fighters who do not give up. Their massive and peaceful mobilizations from their territories of origin to the cities of Cali and Bogota, place them as indigenous people who fight for their rights, for their territories and for social and territorial justice.

Their harmonization practices, their rituals of gratitude to Mother Earth such as the Saakhelu, the Sek Buy and the consecration of the sticks, and the navel-burning to the world at birth, are practices that anchor them to the earth and allow them to be and continue being the Nasa of Colombia who do not give up and who survive despite the systematic death of the leaders who fight to harmonize their territories so that they can live in peace.

The forms of struggle for their territories are carried out through peaceful mobilizations, presenting demands to the competent entities and as a way to make themselves visible and be seen. They also make their responses through the liberation of mother earth, "entering the farms and cutting down cane. Settling in, building shacks, planting food. Taking care of those lands and the beings that inhabit them. Since we settled in those lands and eradicated sugarcane in thousands of hectares, a diversity of plants grows again, the displaced animals return, insects and bees pollinate, the water springs up again.

Mother Earth regenerates and gives us a gift of her abundance. We observe and learn (Pedagogy Release, 2024, P. 22).

One of the fundamental principles of life as peoples is identity insofar as it makes one think as an indigenous person, act as an indigenous person, live as an indigenous person, that is to say, to be indigenous. Being indigenous allows not only to identify oneself as indigenous but also as a people, as an organization to unite, to fight for rights as indigenous, as peoples. This process of identity construction has allowed for exercises of recognition of one's own in all spaces and has served to forge unity and fight for rights (Palechor, 2020, p. 78).

The Nasa People know the dynamics of capitalism, but resist this form of accumulative exchange that, in addition, crosses the dynamics of mother earth and undermines it for the benefit of the holders/owners of the land. Extractivist economies are outside of ancestral practices because they are considered to inflict pain to mother earth and nature, the damage to ecosystems is unforgivable and that is why the earth cries, the environmental crisis is understood from the indigenous peoples as the crisis of man that deteriorates nature and the forms of life.

Nasa resistance practices are precisely focused on valuing the land as the mother that makes life possible, therefore, nature cannot be the property of a few and neither can natural resources such as water, wind, plants. The indigenous economy is based on the land, which is what allows food autonomy and the strengthening of their own. Thinking and acting Nasa implies building life in common for the beings, for the families, for the community, for the people and for Colombians, welcoming the mandates, healing the land and working for the harmony of all.

Territorial struggles in the indigenous reserves are raised through community organization and the defense of their rights. The Nasa have developed their own ways of dealing with conflicts, such as the creation of the indigenous guard, which are community protection groups, and the promotion of dialogues with the State and other actors to seek solutions. Their struggle is a reflection of indigenous resistance to oppression and the search for a future in which they can live in peace and dignity in their ancestral territories.

References

Ariza, L. (2009) Derecho, saber e identidad indígena. Siglo del Hombre.

Manuel Quintín Lame (2017) Los pensamientos del indio que se educó dentro de las selvas colombianas. Editorial University of Cauca.

Palechor, L. (2020) in: Sentires y Pensares. Weaving memories. Universidad Autónoma Indígena Intercultural del Consejo Regional del Cauca.

Sánchez, G. (2021) Caminos de Guerra, utopías de paz. Colombia: 1948-2020. E-. Planeta

S/A (2024) Liberation of pedagogy. Process of liberation of Mother Earth. Ed. Liberation Point. Conversations with indigenous leaders of the Nasa People, 2015, 2019, 2019, 2022, 2024 and 2025. INDEPAZ: <https://indepaz.org.co/observatorio-de-derechos-humanos-y-conflictividades/> HUMAN RIGHTS REPORT (2024)

From Extractivism to Community-based Tourism: Territorial Contestations and Socio-ecological Transitions in the Indigenous Community of Alto Milluni in the Katari Basin - Lake Titicaca, El Alto - Bolivia

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Alto Milluni. The Peri-urban Indigenous Community

The "Comunidad Indígena Originaria de Alto Milluni" is one of the rural communities of the municipality of El Alto. This community is located in District 13 of this municipality, which is known for its rapid growth and its struggles against the privatisation of gas and water in the early 2000s; District 13 is the largest and least inhabited district of the municipality. The Indigenous Community is located at the headwaters of the Katari Basin, which flows into Lake Titicaca.

Alto Milluni is one of the communities in the Basin most affected by more than a century of mining and water extractivism, which have produced water and soil contamination with very high levels of acidity and degradation due to inadequately treated environmental liabilities (Revilla: 2021, 2023). Alto Milluni has been for years a space for the installation of "operational landscapes" (Brenner and Katsikis, 2020) functional to the needs of the capital and the city of La Paz (Revilla, 2023).

These pastoral communities have been also seriously affected by the effects of climate change and urban expansion. These effects include the shrinking of glaciers, drought and the reduction of wetlands and

communal water sources due to the unconsulted extraction of water by the public water company to cover the demand and management of drinking water for consumption in the cities of La Paz and El Alto. Moreover, livestock farming, the community's main source of livelihood, is threatened by the lack of water and attacks by feral dogs from the outskirts of El Alto. In a single attack, the community can lose up to 60 animals.

According to the 2012 Census, the Alto Milluni Community has a total population of 347 people. Of which 188 are men and 159 are women. Most of the livestock species are llamas (2609), sheep (877) and alpacas (435). Furthermore, 45% of the water supply comes from wells or wells. While 43% is supplied by springs coming from thaws or similar. 91.2% do not have electricity.

The threats to livelihoods in Milluni are many and long-standing. Since the establishment of the La Fabulosa mine in the early 20th century, camelid breeding has had to adapt to the fact that several of the water sources and streams were altered by mining activity (IIADI, 2022).

Alto Milluni is severely affected by mining, water extractivism, climate change, and territorial conflicts.

Visitors receive coca leaf and instructions from former miners and community authorities before entering the abandoned Alto Milluni mine. Photo: IIADI - FAADU, UMSA

Entrance to the abandoned mine. Photograph: IIADI - FAADU, UMSA

A mining company that operates in the area with the removal and exploitation of "landslides" (tailings and waste) has expanded its squares into unauthorised fiscal and communal zones and has restricted access to them for local miners through legal proceedings and threats to their safety. This same company not only appropriates the territory, but also transports the waste from the landslides to the Pallina River in the middle part of the basin, contributing to the contamination of the Titicaca.

Urban speculators have sought to appropriate communal land for sale under the pretext that it belongs to neighbouring communities, generating inter-communal conflicts. As a result, there have been violent incursions into Milluni's territory, attempting to displace the community members from their territory, which has led to personal injury and severe material and personal damage.

Answering from the complexities of Identity

The high Andean pastoralist community of Alto Milluni, as usually happens with communities permeated by extractive activity, together with the impact on their livelihoods, find themselves in the need to change their economic activity, often towards the same extractive activity that modifies their territory and their livelihoods, either as wage earners or through other forms of associativity, such as cooperativism in the case of this community.

According to the 2013 Agricultural Census, out of a total of 316 people, some 284 (89%) are engaged in livestock farming as their main activity.

Among the secondary activities of this population, 17% are engaged in mining. 50% of the population are engaged in commerce and 47% in other services. While livestock farming is carried out by women with the support of men, mining is mainly a male activity. Therefore, it is the men who have had to adapt to the pressures of the extractive dynamic to a greater extent.

In times of rising international prices for minerals such as zinc, tin and manganese, some poor community members turn to artisanal mining, but also small and medium-sized mining companies do so without any kind of consultation, giving rise to conflicts with the communities.

Despite the multiple socio-environmental pressures of extractivism and living in the expansion area of one of the fastest growing cities in the country, Alto Milluni has not ceased to consider itself an indigenous community. On the contrary, like Puchukollo in the southern periphery, it has reinforced its indigenous Aymara identity. This identity has not been strengthened by isolation or by the resurgence of a folkloric essentialism, but by the often violent contact with the effects of peripheral urbanisation, mining and hydraulic infrastructures at the service of the cities.

As part of the protest against decades of extractivism, Alto Milluni is represented and redefined as a community with an enormous tourist potential that is expressed in its natural landscapes, sacred sites, rituals and cultural practices, but also in the old mining camp, the dams, tunnels and mining galleries implemented throughout the 20th century, its historic cemetery where the remains of the miners murdered in the massacre of 24 May 1965 for opposing the military dictatorship are buried.

The Milluni Cemetery was declared Cultural Tourist Heritage of the city of El Alto. At the same time, the community of Alto Milluni is located on the route that connects to other tourist attractions of high demand such as the mountains of Chacaltaya and Huayna Potosí and the Charquini snow-capped mountain.

View of the old Alto Milluni mining camp and mill along with the lagoon. Photo: IIADI - FAADU, UMSA

Tourism: community initiatives and policy partnerships

Based on these premises, Alto Milluni seeks to make a transition from decades of extractivism to a more sustainable option founded on community organisation, which contributes not only to the socio-environmental well-being of the community but of the entire Lake Titicaca Basin that receives its waters.

In 2022, the community has started a community tourism project which, although it is an initiative, has received support from different organisations, such as the Gregoria Apaza Promotion Centre, which has helped to equip its culinary infrastructure, has trained the community in gastronomy and in the development of a textile brand.

Recently, the community has formed two groups to promote the management and execution of tourism services in a communal way: The 'Suma Phukhu Milluni' Gastronomic, the Handicraft Centre led by 36 women, and "Miner for a day" led by 20 former mine workers and community members.

Subsequently,² since 2021, IIADI has initiated a collaboration with Alto Milluni, to address the problem of feral dogs through the design of technological devices. Lately, in coordination with the Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning of the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés (UMSA) and IIADI, proposals for projects and materials that are the basis of this community proposal have been designed. At the same time, in agreement with two thesis students from the Tourism course at the Public University of El Alto, proposals for the improvement of the community's tourism services are being evaluated and made.

Thus, after several workshops for the participatory construction of proposals, three routes have been defined to be implemented progressively: Route 1: Jilarata Viewpoint, Milluni Historic Cemetery, Mining Museum, Mine Entrance "Miner for a Day", 'Suma Phukhu Milluni' Gastronomic and Handicraft Centre; Route 2 (Bicycle Tour): Jilarata Viewpoint, Milluni

Historic Cemetery, Milluni Hostel, Ex Estuquera, Laguna Escondida; Route 3 (Trekking): Jilarata Viewpoint, Swing to the Void, Huaca, Stone House, Chacaltaya. Despite this policy of alliances, it is the Board of Directors of the community that leads the whole process. This group, together with other community members, who know the routes, the times and the needs of each point, will reconstruct the historical memory of the tourist attractions to be presented in the community museum.

For the future, what the community proposes is to strengthen community tourism through training/strengthening of services and tourist attention, and equipping the infrastructure of the proposed routes (signage, safety equipment, handrails, ropes, ladders, mining clothing, lighting, counters, lockers, furniture, etc.).

This policy of alliances, including that of IIADI and the Contested Territories network, aims to remedy the environmental situation of the entire Katari Basin and Lake Titicaca, striving for the scaling up and replication of different community proposals coordinated with local and national authorities.

The notion of Territorial Contestation in the light of the experience of Alto Milluni

Alto Milluni's response is based on strengthening cohesion, identity and local resources, not only to denounce and confront these threats, but also to redefine the history of exploitation and open up alternatives for collective and community well-being.

The response is not a denial of dispossession in favour of an ancestralism for tourists, but to turn the vestiges of dispossession into elements for the reconstruction and reflection of collective history. This contestation also implies isolation, articulation and a broad policy of alliances in the face of the multiple threats that face the communities in Alto Milluni. It is also a process of protest, mobilisation and resistance, which includes proposal building and negotiation.

References

Brenner, N. and Katsikis, N. (2020). Operational Landscapes: Hinterlands of the capitalocene. in e. Wall (ed.), The landscapists. Redefining Landscape Relation (pp. 21 - 31).

IIADI (2022). Diagnosis of the Katari Basin. Situación de las Comunidades afectadas por la Contaminación. La Paz.

Revilla, C. 2008. Process of demanding access to drinking water for the neighbourhood councils of the city of El Alto and the expulsion of the company Aguas del Illimani. Informe de Trabajo. La Paz: Unitas/PIDHDD/Oxfam-Novib.

Revilla, C. (2011). Understanding the Mobilizations of October 2003: Dynamic Pressures and Shifting Leadership Practices. In Fabricant and Gustafson eds, El Alto in Remapping Bolivia: Resources, Territory, and Indigeneity in a Plurinational State pp. 116-140, Santa Fe, School for Advanced Research.

Revilla, C. (2023). Aproximaciones a los Mecanismos de Desigualdades Socio-ecológica Urbano - Rural: Lecciones desde la Cuenca Katari en La Paz, Bolivia. Revista UMBRALES 40(Desigualdades):101 - 130. DOI: 10.53287/tpko4631jf45

Revilla, C. (2021). Are we ourselves: Socio-ecological inequalities and urbanisation in the Katari River Basin. Centro de Estudios para el Desarrollo Laboral y Agrario, La Paz.

Life Strategies as Forms of Daily Response to Situations of Poverty and Inequality. The case of the Metropolitan Region of Cochabamba⁵

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The department of Cochabamba in Bolivia is the third most populated department in the country, after Santa Cruz and La Paz, with a projected population of 2,207,028 inhabitants by 2025 (GADC, 2022). It has 16 provinces, 47 municipalities and a Territorio Indígena Originario Campesino (TIOC), distributed in five regions: Metropolitan, Valleys, Tropic, Southern Cone and Andean (GADC, 2019, 2022). Among the five regions, the Metropolis would comprise 66% of the population. The Metropolitan Region of Cochabamba (RMC) is made up of seven municipalities, which is why it is a key space for analysing social, economic and territorial dynamics.

Bolivia faces a trajectory marked by territorial and economic inequalities that have shaped its current social and spatial dynamics, originating in colonial times and still ongoing. These dynamics of exclusion have intensified with accelerated urbanisation and territorial fragmentation, consolidating gaps between urban centres and impoverished peripheries.

Cochabamba has experienced rapid urban growth, driven by internal migration from rural areas to the city. This process has generated a peripheral expansion characterised by a lack of planning and unequal access to basic services such as water, electricity and transport. These conditions have deepened the gap between the urban centre, which concentrates most of the economic opportunities, and the peripheral areas, where most of the impoverished areas are located.

Despite efforts and advances in poverty reduction policies, Bolivia remains one of the poorest countries in the region. According to UDAPE data, between 2006 and 2017, extreme poverty has decreased from almost 37.7% to 17.1%, and poverty from 59.9% to 36.4%. According to the Unsatisfied Basic Needs Index (NBI) in 2012, 44.9%

Cochabamba faces rapid urban growth, poverty, and persistent structural inequalities despite policy efforts.

were in poverty and according to CEDLA's Multidimensional Poverty Index (IPM) (2021), 53.7% were multidimensionally poor in 2019. In the case of Cochabamba, poverty affects a significant part of the population (45.5% as of 2012, according to the NBI). Specifically, this study identifies that more than 75% of those surveyed in the Cochabamba Metropolitan Region (CMR) perpetuate poverty over time, while less than 25% manage to overcome it throughout their life trajectory.

These data show that, regardless of the different approaches used to measure poverty, approximately half of the Bolivian - and Cochabamba's - population is living in poverty, highlighting the vulnerable conditions in which millions of people live, many of whom are forced to make economic decisions for survival. This panorama highlights the persistence of structural inequalities that particularly affect certain groups and territories.

The problem of poverty is structural and it is difficult to identify a single cause, nor does this study pretend to do so. However, it could be mentioned that part of the problem has to do with dynamics that perpetuate inequalities in access to essential common goods such as land, water and basic services. These inequalities not only generate disparities in the distribution of resources, intensified by processes of accelerated urbanisation and economic growth, but also consolidate a territorial accumulation that marginalises peripheral communities, limiting their opportunities for development and reproducing conditions that perpetuate poverty.

[5] This analysis is part of a doctoral study within the framework of the PhD in Social Sciences and Humanities, UMSS-ASDI, which is still in progress.

[6] This study also specifically examines other aspects that, both as a consequence and as a cause, are related to structural poverty, including subjective dimensions.

Economic growth and unplanned urbanisation have consolidated an unequal appropriation, where peripheral communities face dispossession and segregation. This generates a type of accumulation that consolidates structural inequalities and limits opportunities for vulnerable populations. What is in dispute is equitable access to common goods and to the resources necessary for human development.

Life strategies as forms of contestation

In this context, we understand everyday contestation as life strategies that people and communities develop to confront the structural barriers that perpetuate exclusion and economic inequality. These strategies include individual actions, such as studying and working at the same time, self-employment, migration, and informal access to resources as a survival reaction to situations of poverty. By focusing on practical and immediate solutions, these responses are not only evidence of resilience, but also reflect forms of resistance to economic and social structures.

This study implemented the "Encuesta Retrospectiva de Condiciones de Vida" (ERCOVI), a survey designed specifically for the purpose of this research. The survey was administered to a sample of 1600 men and women over the age of 50 in the seven municipalities of the RMC. The retrospective methodology provides a holistic view that relates past experiences to the current situation, showing how decisions and actions over time can mitigate the effects of poverty and transform living conditions.

Although everyday coping practices as life strategies can be developed by people of all ages (from children to older adults), this study focuses specifically on middle-aged and older men and women. This approach is justified because it seeks to analyse life trajectories, exploring how their experiences, decisions and strategies over time have influenced their current situation. Additionally, it provides a comprehensive perspective on the factors that have shaped their evolution and responsiveness to situations of poverty and inequality.

These practices, which may include self-management of basic resources, community organisation, the combination of work and educational activities, the search for alternative income generation strategies, livelihood strategies, migration and labour mobility, support networks, not only challenge the dynamics of accumulation that perpetuate poverty, but also demonstrate the resilience and agency of the most vulnerable populations.

Although these responses do not always seek to directly confront the structures that generate poverty, they constitute acts of resistance that mitigate its effects and reconfigure, from the local scale, the living conditions of those who implement them. Recognising these responses as forms of adaptation and social transformation is essential for designing public policies that not only combat poverty, but also strengthen the capacities of communities to overcome their conditions of vulnerability.

Reflection

In the Cochabamba Metropolitan Region (CMR), the dynamics are deeply related to the processes of capitalist accumulation, which perpetuate structural inequalities and marginalise the most vulnerable population and communities. The unequal appropriation of common goods, such as land, water and basic services, generates fragmented territories where peripheral populations face greater barriers to access opportunities and improve their living conditions.

Faced with these conditions, communities develop practices of daily contestation that are expressed in concrete and adaptive actions to confront territorial inequalities. The self-management of basic resources, solidarity support networks and the combination of work and educational activities are examples of strategies that challenge the dynamics of territorial accumulation and allow individuals and families to mitigate the effects of poverty from the local level.

The practices of daily contestation not only challenge the dynamics of territorial accumulation, but also reflect the fact that the population is not only a recipient of inequalities. They are active actors who seek to transform their reality through resilient practices. In this sense, territories are not only scenarios of exclusion. They are also spaces where communities reinterpret and reconfigure their relationship with resources and development.

It is evident that the livelihood strategies developed by people in contexts of poverty are expressions of resilience and agency that challenge structural inequalities. This identification of cases could be a key contribution to the formulation of inclusive policies and approaches that recognise local capacities, as well as the skills and networks that develop and foster social cohesion. At the same time, it reinforces the need to understand poverty with a multidimensional, dynamic and medium- and long-term approach, where reduction strategies are closely linked to the capacities and potential of individuals and communities.

Oil exploitation in the Ecuadorian Amazon

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The dominant type of territorial accumulation in the north of the Ecuadorian Amazon has been oil exploitation since the 1960s. The conflict unleashed by oil activity is based on its contamination, because wherever oil is extracted, water sources are polluted, affecting particularly peasant populations, and even more so in the case of indigenous peoples in isolation who need hunting animals and water directly from the rivers, leaving everything poisoned.

The benefits of oil exploitation accrue to the importing countries, which have industrial processes capable of producing higher added value. In Ecuador, a minimal percentage has traditionally remained only from extraction. Although in the progressive period this percentage increased notably with respect to the transnational companies that dominate the oil market, the country still did not manage to incorporate industrial processing processes.

In this way, oil exploitation leaves enormous problems of pollution, disease and impoverishment, with minimal oil revenues remaining in a number of middle and upper class areas of the country, with the oil-producing Amazon absorbing the worst consequences (Martín Beristain et al., 2009). This requires profound territorial control to ensure that the machinery can enter, operate and maintain the oil installations, which must be pumped continuously, so that spatio-temporal control becomes a requirement in which the national state is heavily involved through its repressive bodies and all its legal machinery of coercion.

Oil exploitation is carried out by collecting oil at a depth of around 3,000 metres in many places, which is processed in stations from where it is piped into oil pipelines. The disappearance of two peoples in isolation, the violent contact of the Waorani nationality, and the generation of even more profound damage have occurred against the indigenous peoples (Wasserstrom, 2016).

The US company Chevron-Texaco, which polluted the Amazon between the 1960s and 1990s, was denounced in 1993 by 30,000 peasants and indigenous people in a process that has become known as "the trial of the century" (Pigrau, 2014). In 2011, the US company was condemned for damage to health and the environment, with 9.5 billion dollars to repair part of the damage caused. The oil company has been able to avoid the compensation, due to the international legal system, corporate advantages and arbitration (Joseph, 2012). However, the struggle against the atrocity generated by the oil company generated a very strong awareness in Ecuador about the reality of exploitation, which has continued through other national and foreign business conglomerates.

National and global awareness has generated new forms of conflict around oil exploitation in the Amazon. The Yasuní-ITT Initiative was the historic agglomeration of national awareness and put on the international agenda to leave oil in the ground in a place of maximum vulnerability-

Community kichwa del río Napo. Photography: Manuel Bayón.

since it is the home to indigenous peoples in isolation and the lagoon area is one of the highest biodiversity in the world (Vallejo et al., 2015). When the progressive government of Ecuador decided to overthrow this initiative, a very different form of conflict emerged, where the state managed to impose its oil hegemony on the communities in the area, which obtained jobs and investments, while at the same time a urban youth emerged, prioritising the indigenous peoples in isolation and biodiversity (Bayón Jiménez & Arrozola Aranzábal, 2020).

Within this myriad of actors there are a multitude of agents and practices of contestation, different in each community and even within communities. But in order to characterise the different forms that can be made visible, four major forms of community-based protest will be outlined. As oil has continued to be extracted in many of the areas where companies have been operating since the 1990s, Amazonian populations involved in oil have tried to demand public investment and rights through different strategies, with bi-provincial strikes to force state promises as the predominant form in the 1990s and 2000s (Widener, 2007).

In the progressive decade, where repressive violence increased at the same time as royalties for the state and communities, community actions focused on receiving jobs or compensation (Lyll, 2020), as well as developing their institutions to improve ways of exercising rights and oil investment that heavily involved the North Amazonian city population (Díaz-Combs, 2023). There were also numerous territories, towards the south and east of the Amazon, that strengthened their strategies of opposition to the oil opening with marches from the Amazon to Quito or with protests at the negotiation sites of the oil rounds (Coba & Bayón, 2020).

In 2013, opposition to oil exploitation in the ITT Block of the Yasuní National Park took the form of street art actions in Quito, Guayaquil, Cuenca and other major cities in the country, followed by the collection of signatures by the Yasunidos collective, which brought together these young urban sectors (Gálvez Mancilla & Bonilla Martínez, 2014).

The ostensibly fraudulent annulment of the signatures broke this popular expression (Sarmiento, 2021). However, there was a continuation through legal and media channels, which finally led to the victory of the referendum that decided in 2023, with 59% of voters at the national level,

Signature delivery Yasunidos. Image: Twitter Yasunidos

"Oil exploitation brings pollution, disease, and impoverishment, while benefits mainly go to importing countries."

to leave the oil in the ground, showing a form of conflict that scales the Amazonian space to debate the general meanings of oil exploitation, climate change and the social and environmental crisis (Coryat, 2015; Moreano Venegas & Bayón, 2021).

The history of oil exploitation in the Amazon causes three reflections on the relationship between territorial accumulation and challenges to capitalism. First, the possibility of curbing corporate power through broad alliances of peasant, indigenous and urban sectors, under common meanings in the midst of an enormous diversity of ways of understanding politics and politics. Second, the importance of the provision of basic services demanded by the populations that have been attacked for decades by oil exploitation, and which can only be provided at present by the states themselves. To leave out the dispute over the state is to fail to understand the material needs of many of the territories. Finally, the holding and victory of the Yasuní referendum, with much larger margins in popular urban neighbourhoods and rural peasant communities, in the midst of an unprecedented economic, social and political crisis in Ecuador, shows how alliances are possible beyond the local conflicts themselves.

The coming together of popular urban sectors and communities around common axes in the face of environmental devastation and the capitalist elites who benefit from it allows us to visualise political alliances that allow us to go beyond the conventional scales of anti-oil struggles in order to re-imagine Ecuador's post-oil futures.

References

- Bayón Jiménez, M., & Aranzola Aranzábal, Í. (2020). Discussion of the multiscale commons from the Territory of Isolated Peoples. *Universitas*, 32, Article 32. <https://doi.org/10.17163/uni.n32.2020.02>
- Coba, L., & Bayón, M. (2020). Kawsak Sacha: La organización de las mujeres en la traducción política de la selva amazónica en el Ecuador. In *Cuerpos, Territorios y Feminismos* (Cruz Hernández and Bayón). Abya Yala.
- Coryat, D. (2015). Extractive Politics, Media Power, and New Waves of Resistance Against Oil Drilling in the Ecuadorian Amazon: The Case of Yasunidos. *International Journal of Communication*, 9. <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/3795>
- Díaz-Combs, C. (2023). "People are no longer quiet: Ordinary environmental citizenship in Lago Agrio, Ecuador. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25148486231160642>
- Gálvez Mancilla, E., & Bonilla Martínez, O. (2014). Yasunidos: The limits of devastation. *Aportes Andinos*, 85-94.
- Joseph, S. (2012). Protracted lawfare: The tale of Chevron Texaco in the Amazon. *Journal of Human Rights and the Environment*, 3(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.4337/jhre.2012.01.03>
- Lyll, A. (2020). Resistance in retrospect: The multitemporality of extractivism in the Amazon. *Íconos - Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 69, 17-34. <https://doi.org/10.17141/iconos.69.2021.4496>
- Martín Beristain, C., Páez, Darío, & Fernández, I. (2009). *Las palabras de la selva: Estudio psicosocial del impacto de las explotaciones petroleras de Texaco en las comunidades amazónicas de Ecuador*. Institute for Development Studies and International Cooperation.
- Moreano Venegas, M., & Bayón, M. (Eds.) (2021). *La explotación del Yasuní en medio del derrumbe petrolero global* (First edition). Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung Ecuador FES-ILDIS.
- Pigrau, A. (2014). The Texaco-Chevron case in Ecuador: Law and justice in the age of globalization. *Revista Catalana de Dret Ambiental*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.17345/rcda1437>
- Sarmiento, M. (2021). La gran farsa de la anulación de las firmas de la consulta por el Yasuní. *PlanV Magazine*. <https://www.planv.com.ec/investigacion/investigacion/la-gran-farsa-la-anulacion-firmas-la-consulta-el-yasuni>
- Vallejo, M. C., Burbano, R., Falconí, F., & Larrea, C. (2015). Leaving oil underground in Ecuador: The Yasuní-ITT initiative from a multi-criteria perspective. *Ecological Economics*, 109, 175-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.11.013>
- Wasserstrom, R. (2016). Waorani Warfare on the Ecuadorian Frontier, 1885-2013. *The Journal of Latin American and Caribbean Anthropology*, 21(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jlca.12217>
- Widener, P. (2007). Oil Conflict in Ecuador: A Photographic Essay. *Organization & Environment*, 20(1), 84-105. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026607300321>

Comparative Notes on Two Narratives in the Eco-territorial Contestation of the Ojos de Mar Wetland in San Antonio

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This text presents a comparative, reflective, and critical analysis of two narratives concerning the socio-environmental conflict at the Ojos de Mar Wetland in San Antonio, Valparaíso Region. The first presents the official version from a socio-technical and institutional perspective, while the second offers a complementary view from a critical-decolonial standpoint, incorporating an ethical-aesthetic approach based on the process that some of the communities that defend this place have developed through art and insurgent planning.

Conceptual tools for a comparative narrative of conflict

Nature, sustainability, and the environmental crisis have turned into 'empty signifiers' (Swyngedouw, 2011) that, rather than contributing to resolving socio-environmental crises, have anchored these issues in seemingly institutionalized solutions that create an illusion of control based on depoliticised, technocratised and sanitised regulations and policies, which distance us from possible solutions as they encourage inaction and the sustainability of the predatory system rather than of life.

Considering the environmental and social urgency that we are experiencing, this displacement and invisibilisation of the conflict and in decline, become serious and unethical given that they threaten social and environmental justice, exacerbate inequalities, and avoid questioning the economic and social systems that generate the crisis. Environmental issues become a "technical issue", leaving aside their political and structural dimensions. It deactivates the possibility of radical transformations, and even criminalises them.

From a critical Latin American perspective, engaging with the concept of the emptied meaning of nature, decolonial theory posits that neo-extractivism and the multiple forms of subjugation and violence

against nature and territories represent the ultimate expression of colonialism that began with the conquest of America and diversified with the multidimensional condition of coloniality as a modern hegemonic project. Alimonda (2011) criticises the Cartesian separation between nature and society, which has been fundamental in Western thought since Modernity. In contrast, he vindicates indigenous and peasant worldviews, which understand nature as an integral part of social, cultural and spiritual life. It proposes a decolonial perspective that makes visible and values local knowledge, resisting the extractivist logics imposed by the global North and national elites.

In coherence with the critical perspectives of Swyngedouw and Alimonda, considering the implied, empirical and practical vocation of the research itself, I build an epistemic and methodological bridge with the artistic practices of expanded mediation (PAMEX) (García-Huidobro & Freire-Smith, 2023) understood as "territorial praxis" (Horn et al., 2021) that challenge the hegemonic forms of knowledge production and transformations with/in the territories in dispute.

"Environmental issues become 'technical', ignoring political dimensions and sustaining the predatory system over life."

Actions of symbolic and material appropriation of the eco-territory Ojos de Mar Wetland and Maipo River Mouth - Photographs Ojos de Mar Foundation

Actions of symbolic and material appropriation of the eco-territory Ojos de Mar Wetland and Maipo River Mouth - Photographs Ojos de Mar Foundation

They are defined as "intra-experiential, processual, flexible, reflexive and collaborative intra-actions, placing meaning in the need of the community, rather than in artistic production with authorship" (García-Huidobro&Freire-Smith, 2023). The mediating role of PAMEX, from this critical and reflexive perspective proposed by the authors, not only poses the capacity to be a bridge between different dimensions of social reality, but also opens up as a space of agency in which the different agents that come into contact and their relationships are transformed.

Territorial praxis" (Horn et al., 2021) defined as concrete ways of thinking-doing that stage the embodied character of territorial knowledge production are at the same time political, ethical and aesthetic. Thinking-doing requires a formal, i.e. aesthetic, decolonisation in order to explore new ways and new languages of knowing, learning, communicating and transforming our relationship with a world in crisis and emergency.

In this sense, artistic practices are fundamental given that they have the capacity to imagine and construct alternative languages in the face of current crises: "Contemporary art is not simply a space of representation, but an experimental terrain where languages are designed that are capable of expressing what cannot yet be said: new sensibilities, ethics and relations with the world that overflow the frameworks of anthropocentric modernity". (Bourriaud, 2020, p. 22). Bourriaud stresses that contemporary art can transcend mere aesthetics to become a means of ethical transformation. From this perspective, artists not only document or criticise crises, but also create new ethical and cultural frameworks that respond to the urgent need to reconfigure our relationship with nature, communities and the planet.

Official narrative: socio-technical genealogy of the socio-environmental conflict in the Ojos de Mar de San Antonio wetland

San Antonio is a coastal city and commune in central Chile, serving as the capital of the Province of San Antonio. It is the busiest container port in the country and, along with the urban areas of Cartagena and Santo Domingo, forms the San Antonio metropolitan area. Historically, it was a place of fishing vocation and peasant traditions, with attractive natural landscapes that were enhanced with tourist infrastructure in the first half of the 20th century. Its port history dates back to the end of the 16th century with the Spanish merchant Antonio Núñez de Fonseca, who set up the first warehouse in San Antonio with the aim of storing agricultural products from the region and salting dried fish.

The importance of San Antonio, as a port, originated in the Chilean-Spanish War in 1865. As the docks and warehouses of Valparaíso had been destroyed by a Spanish bombardment, there was no choice but to use San Antonio as the main port. During the 20th century the focus was on providing infrastructure and connectivity to the port to support Valparaíso's port operation. Social and urban development was always in the shadow of port development, which became more acute from the 1980s onwards when the neo-liberal model boosted foreign trade in Chile.

Over the past decade, the San Antonio Port Company (EPSA), established in 1997 under Law No. 19.542 on the 'Modernization of the State Port Sector,' has been advancing a port expansion project known as the Outer Port Project (PE), also referred to as the Large-Scale Port or Megaport, which involves a state investment of around US\$ 3,500 million.

The project in question involves in its design the fragmentation of the Maipo River mouth ecosystem, the dredging of the seabed in an area of influence and environmental impact of between 5 and 10 km², the industrial use and construction of the entire coastal edge of the commune of San Antonio, completely eliminating its beaches, diverting the course of the Maipo River mouth and producing significant and irreversible environmental, patrimonial, cultural and social impacts for the territory.

The PE project is currently on hold and under reconsideration due to the more than 3,000 citizen observations made in 2021 and 3,000 more in 2022 after the first Addendum, presented in the Citizen Participation processes convened by the Environmental Impact Assessment System (SEIA for its acronym in Spanish), due to the serious socio-environmental impacts of this project.

In 2019, the socio-environmental conflict was officially recorded in the National Institute of Human Rights' conflict map. That December local residents voiced their opposition to the port expansion project, primarily through a national plebiscite convened by the Association of Chilean Municipalities for the new constitution and plebiscite with local consultations, where 97% of the 20,400 Sanantoninos and Sanantoninas who voted approved the consultation to protect the Ojos de Mar Wetland, mouth, beach, estuary and DYR park to have the urban park of the city of San Antonio there.

In 2020, The "Empresa Portuaria San Antonio" presented the Environmental Impact Study for the project, which was declared admissible by the Environmental Assessment Service. Various civil society organisations, such as the NGO Ojos de Mar, Sindicato de Pescadores de la Boca del Maipo and Agrupación Calaucán de Pueblos Originarios, have denounced from social demonstrations to the formal presentation of observations to the SEIA that the industrial port activity affects the ecosystem and the endemic flora and fauna of the wetland, nominated as a "Western Hemisphere Shorebird Reserve Network" (WHSRN).

Parallel to the Environmental Assessment process in 2021, a legal claim process was initiated against the Ministry of the Environment for the rejection of the declaration of Urban Wetland requested by the communities through the Municipality of San Antonio, which lasted more than two years and on May 10, 2024 the resolution of the Second Environmental Court was published in the Official Journal of the Republic of Chile to declare the Lagoon System as an Urban Wetland under Law No. 21.202 as Ojos de Mar Urban Wetland, titled by the national press as "Environmental Victory" and "Citizen Triumph".

This chronological trajectory of the socio-environmental conflict in San Antonio is accurate in terms of socio-technical data, however, it is not clear what is really in dispute, nor the multiple communicational, cultural, academic and political strategies that the communities have developed

"The industrial port activity threatens the wetland ecosystem, sparking legal battles and citizen resistance."

to defend it. From a critical point of view, we could analyse that there is a risk of institutionalisation of socio-environmental conflicts. Entering institutional protocol and being brought before the courts can lead to encapsulation rather than openness and a call to the communities.

Other assesments and narratives

Artistic activities in defence of the Ojos de Mar Wetland 2020-2024

Thus far, socio-environmental activism in San Antonio has primarily relied on scientific and regulatory frameworks, and multiple strategies and alliances have been developed with research centers, universities, environmental defense foundations, and international programmes for the protection of wetlands and coastal ecosystems. However, this first scientific-normative line is more external and alien to the territory.

Given the above, the communities and environmental organisations have developed a line of socio-cultural, patrimonial and artistic action, under the premise of re-linking ourselves WITH nature and WITH the territory, from its multiple socio-environmental and biocultural, ancestral, spiritual, aesthetic and sensitive dimensions. Art has operated in the socio-environmental conflict of the wetland as a theoretical-practical platform that allows, on the one hand, to explore the relational-conflictive assemblages of the territory (Baker & McGuirk, 2017)

FONDART Ecosensory Art Project 2022-2024
Ana Laura Galarza-Jocelyne Rodríguez Droguett

and, on the other, to test a productive conflict understood as a field of frictions that can produce unexpected alliances, without seeking to eradicate the conflict with easy or partial solutions: to build through conflict (Tsing 2017; 2021).

In this context, artistic practices associated with socio-environmental activism in San Antonio—including mural design and painting, campaigns to create and install community signage, "Ecosensory Art" mediations, soundscapes, performances and participatory sculpture, among others, can also be understood as "territorial praxis" insofar as they go beyond the artistic sphere and dialogue with what Miraftab (2018) defines as "insurgent planning" as actions with symbolic implications; can also be understood as "territorial praxis" insofar as they exceed the artistic sphere and dialogue with what Miraftab (2018) defines as "insurgent planning" as actions with symbolic and material implications of territorialisation of the place, which operate as seeds of a "decolonisation of the imagination".

In this way, in the socio-environmental conflict of the Ojos de Mar Wetland, the communities not only act for the conservation and protection of a supposed

"protection polygon of the Urban Wetland" imposed by the environmental institutions, but also promote insurgent practices-thinking-imaginary-plans for the regeneration of the dunes, water eyes (menokos in mapudungun), forests, ecological niches and affective multi-species relationships that defy the classifications and polygons in which the diversity of life does not fit, weaving complex, entangled, dynamic and resilient

eco-territories
Narrating WITH the feet IN the territory/Narrating WITH the territory IN the feet

I have co-inhabited the eco-territory of the mouth of the Maipo River and the town of Lloleco since 2014. For the last five years my professional work in art and cultural management has been focused on the defense of the ecosystem of the mouth of the Maipo River, especially on its northern shore (San Antonio), which is very affected by the activity of the current port and threatened by the port expansion project.

Community cultural management, activism through PAMEX and currently research-action (as a doctoral student in Territory, Space and Society at the University of Chile) have been the path that this territory has marked for me, which together with the communities that defend life we have woven, understanding that the defence of life against the predatory system must multiply the paths and strategies, inhabiting every interstice and crevice with sensitivity and creativity.

Building knowledge WITH our feet in the territory and WITH the territory in our hearts, in a place where socio-cultural development has been denied in pursuit of economic development (promised, but never fulfilled) is also an insurgent, contesting and activist practice. Defending life requires making the body, mind and heart available, for which art as a practice and other-form of knowledge allows us to articulate and sustain a creative and sensitive defence that explores the aesthetic forms of the urgent ethical and political transFORMations that are called for from all the sciences.

Some of our advocacy actions have been the creation of community murals around biocultural themes, artistic mediations around climate action activities such as beach clean-ups and participatory methodologies of co-creation of artistic works to raise awareness through the body and emotions (Ecosensory Art).

"Artistic activism fosters insurgent planning, regenerating ecosystems and challenging imposed environmental classifications."

In December 2024 we realised together with Cecilia Vicuña the "Quipu de Encuentro Llolleo" as a poetic-political action of physical reconnection of the lagoons and the sea in the Ojos de Mar Wetland and Llolleo Beach.

PAMEX Ecosensorials narrated in the first person

Actions of symbolic and material appropriation of the eco-territory Ojos de Mar Wetland and Maipo River Mouth - Photographs Ojos de Mar Foundation

We gathered in the open classroom of the Ojos de Mar Wetland for the fourth community workshop on "Ecosensory Art" (Regional FONDART Project for creation in the visual arts). It was the turn of sensory exploration through the sense of sight, as in previous workshops we had explored taste, touch and hearing in other threatened landscapes and socio-ecosystems in the Province of San Antonio.

We used cardboard viewfinders to focus our gaze and visually scan the landscape and its violent contrasts: lagoons, trucks, reeds, reedbeds, countiners, flocks of birds, cranes. From a distance, the black cardboard scopes looked like binoculars, like those used in the bird censuses that are also carried out in July every year.

They could also be read as symbolic devices of a counter-surveillance of the security cameras installed by the San Antonio port company (EPSA) to "monitor" our actions. And as we turned to the west, with our non-magnifying viewfinders we could also frame the seascape with the Chemamüll that the Mapuche Lafkenche communities installed at the last Wüñol Tripantu, staring towards the port cranes to the north, also as a sign of counter-surveillance.

"Defending life demands embodied, creative resistance—art as insurgent knowledge, interweaving activism, territory, and sensitivity to counteract socio-environmental injustices and reclaim spaces for biocultural coexistence and transformation."

Actions of symbolic and material appropriation of the eco-territory Ojos de Mar Wetland and Maipo River Mouth - Photographs Ojos de Mar Foundation

Websites

1. <https://mapaconflictos.indh.cl/#/conflicto/25805>
2. <https://www.puertosanantonio.com/cronologia-del-proyecto>
3. <https://www.sanantonio.cl/municipalidad/noticias/item/8798-resultados-oficiales-de-la-consulta-ciudadana-en-san-antonio.html>
4. <https://sanantonio.cl/nacimiento-del-puerto-de-san-antonio.html>
5. <https://www.diariooficial.interior.gob.cl/publicaciones/2024/05/10/43847/01/2489535.pdf>
6. <https://www.fima.cl/2023/11/29/victoria-ambiental-para-san-antonio-comunidad-logra-que-los-ojos-de-mar-sean-considerados-humedal-urbano/>
7. <https://eldesconcierto.cl/2023/07/22/triunfo-ciudadano-empresa-portuaria-de-san-antonio-acepta-proteger-humedal-ojos-de-mar>

References

- Alimonda, H. (2011). *Colonised Nature. Ecología Política y minería en América Latina*. Buenos Aires: CLACSO.
- Bourriaud, N. (2020). *Inclusions. Aesthetics of the capitalocene*. Adriana Hidalgo editora: Buenos Aires.
- Carvajal, S., & Parrini, G. (2023, April 2). San Antonio: the laments of a failed city. *La Tercera*. <https://www.latercera.com/san-antonio-los-lamentos-de-una-ciudad-fallida>
- García-Huidobro-Munita, R., Freire-Smith, M. (2023). "Hacia prácticas artísticas de mediación en contextos sociales, Arte, Individuo y Sociedad". On-line publication, 1-20. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5209/aris.85576>
- Horn, P., De Carli, B., Habermehl, V., Lombard, M., Roberts, P., & Téllez Contreras, L. F. (2021). *Territories in dispute: Interdisciplinary dialogues on conflict, resistance and alternatives. Lessons from Latin America (Contested Territories Working Paper Series, No. 001)*. University of Sheffield.
- Martínez Alier, J., & Palacios Páñez, M. (2011). *El ecologismo de los pobres: conflictos ambientales y lenguajes de valoración (5th ed. amp.)*. Icaria.
- Miraftab, F. (2018). Insurgency, planning and the prospect of a humane urbanism. *Territories* 38, 215-233.
- Mujica de la Fuente, Juan (1947). *El puerto de San Antonio*. Santiago: Imprenta El Esfuerzo.
- Pino Lagos, V. de los Á. (2023). *Expansión portuaria en San Antonio: La controversia por el desarrollo (Journalism degree dissertation)*. Universidad de Chile, Faculty of Communication and Image, School of Journalism.
- Rodrigo, J. & Collados, A. (2015). Challenges and complexities of collaborative artistic practices and collective pedagogies. *Pulso*, 38, 57-72.
- Svampa, M. (2012). Commodity Consensus, Ecoterritorial Turn and Critical Thinking in Socio-environmental Movements in Latin America. *Revista del Observatorio Social de América Latina (OSAL)*, Year XIII N°32, November 2012, pages 15-38. DOI: <https://biblioteca.clacso.edu.ar/clacso/osal/20120927103642/OSAL32.pdf>
- Svampa, M. (2021): "Feminismos ecoterritoriales en América Latina. Entre la violencia patriarcal y extractivista y la interconexión con la naturaleza", *Documentos de Trabajo*, nº 59 (2nd period), Madrid, Fundación Carolina.
- Swyngedouw, E. (2011) Nature does not exist! Sustainability as Symptom of a Depoliticized Planning/Nature does not exist! Sustainability as Symptom of a Depoliticized Planning. *Urban*, (01), 41-66.
- Tsing, A. L. (Ed.) (2017). *Art of Living on a Damaged Planet: Ghosts and Monsters of the Anthropocene*. University of Minnesota Press, 348 pages.
- Tsing, A. L. (2021). *The Mushroom at the End of the World: On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins*. Editorial Captain Swing. 400 pages.

Countering Peri-urban Extractivism: Practices of Re-appropriation around the Colina River

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The conflict takes place around the Colina river, located in the commune of the same name, on the northern outskirts of Santiago, in the face of the expansion of different extractivist frontiers on the metropolitan fringes. These frontiers are driven by large-scale mining, agro-industry and the development of gated communities. The convergence and overlap of these phenomena, which can be conceptualised as "peri-urban extractivism", affects a significant environment for some inhabitants and turns the river into a contested space in a context marked by prolonged water scarcity and overexploitation.

Territorial accumulation around the Colina River is primarily evident in the unequal appropriation of common goods, especially water, but also soil and landscape. Agro-industry extracts large volumes of water for intensive irrigation (Iriarte, 2022), while mining has generated episodes of contamination of the river in 2016, 2021 and 2024 due to toxic waste flows towards the tailings dam "Las Tórtolas", north of the city (Arriaza, 2024; Pérez, 2021). Meanwhile, in the urban area, the development of gated communities has transformed the river landscape over the last decade, building an extensive and illegal wall of earth along the riverbed to "cover" the city in full view of the authorities and the indignation of some neighbours (Arce, 2017).

This creates tensions between market-driven logics that promote the privatisation and alteration of common goods, and community logics that seek to sustain socio-ecological practices linked to the river and other ways of conceiving nature. In this context, the NGO Investiga Colina, made up of professional inhabitants from different parts of the commune, seeks to have the Colina River declared a Protected Wildlife Area (ASP), in order to safeguard its biodiversity and make its ecological importance visible in the face of the advance of intensive economic activities. This is one of a wider repertoire of practices carried out by Investiga Colina in order to make the ecological and symbolic value of the river visible, as well as to challenge the advance of peri-urban extractivism.

Colina River sluice gate: The Colina River sluice gate diverts the watercourse to underground aqueducts that supply agribusiness.

The Colina River conflict involves extractivist activities like mining, agro-industry, and gated communities, creating tensions over water and land.

Some of these practices were experimented by members of Contested_Territories in April 2024 in the context of the meeting "Metodologías Otras: Disputas territoriales, diálogo de saberes y futuros" organised by the Nodo de la Universidad de Chile, an opportunity in which we were welcomed by the NGO in Colina to learn more about their motivations and about the territory they seek to protect.

The advancing frontiers of peri-urban extractivism

In March 2011, the Chilean government declared Colina a water-stressed area, meaning that the demand for water exceeds the amount available, placing climate change as one of the main causal factors, but the causes that led to the overexploitation of the Colina River and the alteration of its landscape go back years, starting with the implementation of neoliberal policies that privatised water in Chile during the 1980s, as well as the liberalisation of the land market and the privatisation of urban planning in the early 2000s (Zunino, 2006; Hildago et al., 2008; Lukas, Fragkou and Vásquez, 2020),

Dry Colina River: The urban section of the Colina River has dried up as a result of the watercourse diversion.

which enabled the construction of residential megaprojects in the area (Naranajo et al., 2024; Lukas, Arce and Pereira, 2024). Since then, Colina has been one of the fastest growing areas in terms of population (Naranajo, 2017).

In recent years, water and landscape exploitation in the Colina river sub-basin has intensified, drastically reducing the flow and leaving sections of the river completely dry, causing a marked contrast between the state of the flow in the urban area and in the upper part of the sub-basin (Iriarte, 2022). In the interior of the river, through the sclerophyllous forest of the Andean foothills, the waters still flow strongly and are used as a popular bathing resort by local inhabitants and visitors.

However, the reason why the flow does not reach the city is due to a nearby sluice gate that diverts the river to an agro-exporting company (as seen in the picture below). It is able to do so because it leases water rights from the Chilean Army, perpetual owners of the waters that irrigate some of the streams in the sub-basin (Fajardo, 2022).

At the same time, the expansion of real estate projects in Colina over the last 20 years has intensified territorial inequalities, with the Chicureo sector, now known as a new upper neighbourhood of Santiago, taking centre stage (Vicencio & Rodríguez, 2023). The contrast in terms of access to services and water between Chicureo and the traditional city and its "urban-rural" localities is extreme.

While gated communities feature artificial lagoons, vast green spaces, equestrian clubs and golf courses, many nearby localities face severe water shortages and rely on water trucks (Nicolás-Artero, 2015).

In the midst of these antagonistic landscapes, a 4-kilometer-long earthen wall was built along the riverbed, blocking the view from gated communities to the traditional city (Chilevisión, 2022), attempting to hide the dry river, the micro-landfills scattered along the riverbed, the riverside immigrant camps, the old neighbouring towns and the city's two emblematic prisons.

This panorama provides a territorial context to problematise the ecological deterioration and the discriminatory transformation of the landscape due to the advance of peri-urban extractivism. Faced with this reality, organisations such as Investiga Colina have taken action through territorial practices aimed at preserving the river, promoting its declaration as an ASP and promoting a change in the way these spaces and the associated ways of life are valued.

Between capitalist and eco-territorial logics

The territorial context of Colina is marked by a complex network of actors involved in an extractivist governance scheme that affects common goods such as water, land for development and landscape. In this model of peri-urban extractivism, the role of local government - of known neoliberal tradition - and the practices of the main companies are fundamental to the advancement of these dynamics. They are equally relevant to understanding the motivations behind local organisation.

Among the prominent actors, the agro-industry Chacabuco Quality Grapes S.A. has been singled out as responsible for the dry state of the Colina River. According to an investigation by Investiga Colina (Iriarte, 2022), the company is one of the main beneficiaries of water rights associated with the river, and is therefore responsible for the operation of the sluice gate that diverts the river to irrigate more than one hundred hectares of grape vineyards exported to China and the United States. It would therefore be responsible for the water flow not reaching the city.

The Colina territory is shaped by extractivist governance, with actors like Chacabuco Quality Grapes S.A. and Anglo American driving water and land exploitation.

Despite the revealing research, NGO members highlight an issue confirmed in informal conversations with local residents: large-scale mining is perceived to be responsible for water scarcity, particularly Anglo American and its "Los Bronces" project, one of the largest copper mines in Chile, located in the Andean foothills of Santiago. Aware of the community sensitivity around this issue, Anglo American has intensified its efforts to legitimise its operations (Rey-Coquais, 2021), making progress in the supply of fully industrial water for its operations and deploying corporate social responsibility strategies, such as the donation of public infrastructure, green areas, services such as schools and health centres, and support to rural communities for water supply. At the same time, in response to citizen complaints, the company has issued statements exonerating itself from episodes of pollution and water shortages, exacerbating its technological efficiency (Anglo American, 2016).

Regarding urban extractivism, real estate development in the Colina district has been driven by major companies in the national market. In the early 2000s, these companies, taking advantage of favorable adjustments in metropolitan urban planning, spearheaded an unprecedented real estate boom that urbanized and expanded Chicureo (Lukas et al., 2024), consolidating it as a new highrise neighbourhood for Santiago.

This expansion turned Chicureo into a branded location, whose influence has extended to other areas of Colina, gradually encroaching upon the traditional urban center. A clear example is the old hamlet of Santa Filomena, located on the other side of the river and adjacent to the city, which has practically disappeared due to the construction of the "Ayres de Chicureo" project.

This development, a gated community of 180 hectares with an artificial lagoon, was carried out by the company FFV. It is worth noting that this same company was pointed out in a television report as being responsible for the construction of the previously mentioned earth wall (Chilevisión, 2022).

Although "Ayres de Chicureo" is on the other side of the river, it is very close to the two prisons of Colina, in an area marked by large informal settlements inhabited mostly by Latin American immigrants. In this sector, the river has dried up, and its waters have been replaced by micro-landfills. Thus, the company not only transformed the river's landscape but also constructed a discriminatory barrier designed to safeguard the profitability of its real estate business—at the expense of concealing surrounding socio-spatial inequalities under layers of earth.

In response to this complex network of actors driving peri-urban extractivism, the NGO Investiga Colina actively challenges its expansion. By adopting a holistic approach and focusing on revaluing Colina's river environment, they have implemented practices that integrate research, education, and activism. In the meeting "Other Methodologies" they shared their experiences with us, which allowed us to visit Colina and stand on the earthen wall, where we saw a fragmented and desolate landscape. There, members of the NGO narrated the way in which the territorial injustice they experience leads to their protest practices based on the affective relationships they have with the territory and their alternative ecological values to market logics on nature. In this sense, it is possible to distinguish at least three types of protest practices in which Investiga Colina is actively involved.

First, the NGO has promoted initiatives to declare the river as an ASP supported by the recent implementation of the Biodiversity and Protected Areas Law in Chile. This initiative aims for the inhabitants and visitors of the Colina River to recognise the sub-basin as a "Nature Sanctuary", seeking to protect biodiversity, water commons and encourage responsible tourism.

Ayres de Chicureo transformed the river landscape, prompting Investiga Colina to challenge extractivism.

Colina River in the upper part of the watershed. This site is significant for local groups seeking its appropriation for environmental education.

Collage: The process of dispossession of the Colina River's water.

Second, Investiga Colina has made urban inequalities visible in its networks, the wall of land as well as the contrast between the dry river in the city and the artificial lagoons in exclusive condominiums, showing how the unequal appropriation of water and landscape are expressions of inequality and territorial injustice.

In this sense, the NGO is involved in instances of citizen participation associated with the modification of the Communal Regulatory Plan that defines land use and the urban boundary. After the "Other Methodologies" meeting, we were invited to one of these instances to learn, together with other organisations, how the authorities and real estate agents communicate the city they conceive and the regulatory adjustments necessary for this, highlighting the technocratic and restricted sense of such meetings.

Third, Investiga Colina organises workshops and educational talks to raise awareness in school communities about the importance of the river as a common good and its key role in the region's ecosystems. The NGO constantly conducts guided visits to the Colina River with students from local schools, teaching them about the flora, fauna, geography and geology of the environment, as well as carrying out clean-up activities.

The case of the Colina river is evidence of the tension between the capitalist logics of accumulation and the practices of territorial re-appropriation led by local organisations.

This spot on the Colina River, known as "Las Compuertas," is valued by local residents as a popular swimming area but is also used by the agroindustry..

Local practices and other ways of conceiving nature

The case of the Colina river is evidence of the tension between the capitalist logics of accumulation and the practices of territorial re-appropriation led by local organisations. These dynamics reflect how the dominant peri-urban extractivism is rapidly transforming the territory, prioritising dispossession, commodification and the manipulation of nature to the detriment of the growing socio-ecological needs that have begun to emerge in some inhabitants in a context of systemic ecological crisis.

The effort to designate the river as a Protected Natural Area is not just a form of resistance; it also redefines the relationship between community, nature, and development. These initiatives are not mere reactions to peri-urban extractivism; they embody acts of resistance that envision alternative territorialities, detached from capitalist logics and rooted in socio-environmental justice and the stewardship of common goods.

This case also invites reflection on grassroot mobilisation strategies and their potential to generate transformative narratives in territories under intense pressure from the exploitation of common goods. Investiga Colina's actions reveal how emotions, collective memories and affective relationships with the territory are fundamental to challenging capitalist structures and envisioning more equitable and ecologically viable futures.

References

- Anglo American (2016). Public Statement: <https://chile.angloamerican.com/medios/press-releases/pr-2016/2016-02-08.aspx>
- Arce, I. (2017) What is an earth wall doing in Colina? Opinion column published in NGO Observatorio Cité: <https://cite.org/blog/2017/01/04/que-hace-un-muro-de-tierra-en-colina/>
- Arriaza, J. (2023). PDI investigates origin and possible contamination after complaint of strange red colour in the waters of the Quilapilún estuary in Colina. *La Tercera*. <https://www.>
- Chilevisión (2022). They call it the "wall of shame": They denounce that the company deposits waste to separate low-income and affluent sectors. Chilevisión. <https://www.chilevision.cl/noticias/nacional/lo-denominan-el-muro-de-la-verguenza-denuncian-que-empresa-deposita>
- Fajardo, M. (2022, 13 September). Estudio científico cuantifica sequía de río Colina, cuyo derechos de agua el Ejército arrienda a terceros. *El Mostrador*. <https://www.elmostrador.cl/cultura/2022/09/13/estudio-cientifico-cuantifica-sequia-de-rio-colina-cuyos-derechos-de-agua-el-ejercito-arrienda-a-terceros/>
- Hidalgo, R., Zunino, H., & Álvarez, L. (2008). Typologies of metropolitan expansion in Santiago de Chile: State precariopolis and real estate privatopolis. *Scripta Nova. Electronic journal of geography and social sciences*, 12(270).
- Iriarte, S. (2022) Why has the Colina River dried up and well levels are dropping day by day? ONG Investiga Colina: <https://investigacolina.org/por-que-se-seco-el-rio-colina-y-los-niveles-de-los-pozos-bajan-dia-a-dia/>
- Lukas, M., Arce, I., & Pereira, V. (2024). Urban financialization and structural speculation: the production of the Piedra Roja megaproject as a 'real estate mall' and the territorial transformation of the northern periphery of Santiago. *Revista de Historia y Geografía*, (51), 115-142. <https://doi.org/10.29344/07194145.51.3942>
- Lukas, M., Fragkou, M., & Vásquez, A. (2020). Towards a political ecology of new urban peripheries: Land, water and power in Santiago de Chile. *Revista de Geografía Norte Grande*, 76, 95-119.
- Naranjo, G. (2017). Urban expansion in Chacabuco: Towards the redefinition of a new territory, 1980-2010 [Doctorate in Architecture and Urban Studies]. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile.
- Naranjo, G. (2017). La expansión urbana en Chacabuco: Hacia la redefinición de un nuevo territorio, 1980-2010 [PhD in Architecture and Urban Studies]. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile. <https://doi.org/10.7764/tesisUC/ARQ/57469>
- Naranjo, G., Bécar, M., Venegas, P., & Díaz, M. (2024). The transformation of Chacabuco: From pre-Columbian village to the metropolitan periphery of Santiago, Chile. *Revista Geográfica de Chile Terra Australis*, 60(1).
- Nicolás-Artero, C. (2015). Memories of water. User organisations facing scarcity in the Chicureo basin, Colina (1962-2015). *Historical time*.
- Pérez, R. (2021). Denuncian presencia de arsénico y aluminio a niveles irregulares en río Colina. *La Nación*. <https://www.lanacion.cl/denuncian-presencia-de-arsenico-y-aluminio-a-niveles-irregulares-en-rio-colina/>
- Rey-Coquais, Solène (2021). Of copper, water and glaciers in the global metropolis. The new role of mega-mining in the environmental governance of Santiago de Chile. *Revista de geografía Norte Grande*, (79), 139-161. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0718-34022021000200139>
- Vicencio, K. M., & Rodríguez, A. V. (2023). Territorial occupation in the Andean foothills: future conurbation in communes of the northeastern sector of the Metropolitan Region of Santiago, Chile? *Ería: Revista cuatrimestral de geografía*, 43(3), 275-291.
- Zunino, H. M. (2006). Power Relations in Urban Decision-making: Neo-liberalism, "Techno-politicians" and Authoritarian Redevelopment in Santiago, Chile. *Urban Studies*, 43(10), 1825-1846. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980600838184>

Environmental problems in the Reconquista river basin. Source: Urban Planning Workshop, 2024.

Listening Practices. Community Learning for a Social Architecture

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The environmental, housing and infrastructure problems are a historical debt in the informal settlements located in the Reconquista river basin, within the metropolitan region of Buenos Aires. Most of these settlements are located in low-lying or flood-prone areas, which have been built on land reclaimed from the river, either by illegal dumping of solid urban waste, demolition waste, rubble or mud. It is also significant that the Reconquista basin is the area where the CEAMSE (center for disposal and treatment of urban solid waste that receives waste from 22 districts with more than 13 tons of daily disposal) and open-air dumps that operate without any type of control are centrally located.

This context of extreme vulnerability is also characterized by the absence of public infrastructure (sanitation, health, education and leisure) and the degradation of common open areas, which consist mainly of streets (mostly dirt), passages, vacant lots and sports fields. These areas suffer from poor conditions due to the absence of pavements and drainage systems, in addition to problems such as flooding, spontaneous garbage dumps, absence of green spaces, difficulties in accessing drinking water, electrical hazards and presence of mosquitoes and rodents, among other needs (Defensoría del Pueblo de la Nación, 2007; Janches, Henderson, MacColman, 2014; Giorno, Dadon, 2016; Morandera et al., 2019).

Although the Municipality of San Martín has a strong presence in territorial management, the size of the demand far exceeds its budget and available resources, so that the neighbors have organized collectively to help alleviate, even if only partially, some of these demands. Generally, these neighborhood organizations are circumscribed to the geographical, temporal and identity limits of each neighborhood and have referents who, with time, become "territorial articulators" before the different municipal authorities.

This form of organization is very powerful and effective because it allows mapping social dynamics in real time and access to information and a very precise knowledge of each family or neighbor living in these neighborhoods. Usually, this information is not possible to obtain through official censuses.

In recent years, the Directorate of Socio-Urban Integration (DISU, MSM) has built a network with all these territorial articulators that has allowed it to identify and prioritize the different demands of the neighbors. However, there are conflicts or needs that require the development of specific collective work methodologies to characterize these problems and understand the complexity of factors and actors involved in order to build a possible solution.

Urban growth of the 8 de Mayo and Costa del Lago neighborhoods between 2004 and 2024. Flooding, March 20, 2024. Source: own elaboration based on Google earth, TV channel América 24 (A24).

In this context, UNSAM have worked in the neighborhoods of 8 de Mayo and Costa del Lago (San Martín), which were selected as pilot cases. The origin of these settlements dates back to the occupation of 8 de Mayo in 1998 and the progressive filling of the Del Libertador lagoon, over which urbanization has continued, leading to several cases of overflowing and flooding (Gutiérrez, Pereyra, Peláez, Scholl, Tassara, 2022). According to the National Registry of Popular Neighborhoods (RENABAP), both neighborhoods house more than 1,400 families in an area of 32 hectares, with a high rate of overcrowded households, precarious housing and unsatisfied basic needs.

The fundamental premise of these works framed in the Contested Territories network is the development of new methodologies that allow the convergence between "popular knowledge", installed in the territory, and "academic knowledge", theory and practices, assuming its political implication and social responsibility. From the popular knowledge, a need arises: to be able to transfer all this tacit knowledge, and its logics, to a technical thinking that allows to translate all those claims and needs into a new agenda located and critical of the prevailing status quo in these vulnerable environments.

The neighbors, the beneficiaries of these projects, are fundamental actors in the problematization of these processes. In this way, their participation is empowered and strengthened, promoting the building of trust and the possibility that the expectations created will not be disappointed. As communication becomes more regular and fluid over time, a dynamic of dialogue and the search for permanent consensus is encouraged. Therefore, these projects make visible and channel responses built from new knowledge.

These answers operate on problems of very different scales, and at the same time complementary: the urban scale and the 1 in 1 scale.

Urban scale. Co-evaluation of public space

Environmental, safety and infrastructure maintenance problems affect the use of public spaces and, consequently, the daily life of residents in informal settlements. Particularly in those located in areas of high environmental risk such as the popular neighborhoods of the Reconquista Basin. There, streets and passages channel the pedestrian mobility of neighbors, while constituting spaces of sociability and expansion of overcrowded houses and small stores or environments located on the first floor, in direct relation to the sidewalk.

In this context, issues affecting the use of public space and pedestrian mobility patterns are being studied through field trips, participatory workshops and audited walks. These methodologies allow an understanding that goes beyond objective data from technical surveys, incorporating the perceptions and experiences of users (Mehta, 2008; Sutherland, Shackelford and Christian Rose, 2017). It should also be clarified that in recent years, cooperatives have led the construction of drinking water and sanitation networks, paving and street lighting, and therefore have acquired specific knowledge and have a skilled workforce.

Through these three activities, a first characterization of the public space is underway, providing own surveys and technical reports or previous research, including variables such as: width and continuity of streets and passages, lighting, presence of micro dumps, types of activities and occupation of the sidewalk,

Workshop organized with DISU at the 8 de Mayo Community Center. Tour with territorial articulators.

flood zones, vegetation and absorbent soil, accessibility and presence of equipment, among others. In parallel, daily pedestrian routes are being identified with the help of territorial articulators, and the perception of neighbors is being recorded through interviews, while they walk the streets and use the public space. The results will be shared and discussed in the upcoming participatory workshops.

In addition, these activities are carried out with local government representatives to develop a mobile application that will make it possible to record the problems that neighbors perceive in the use of public space in real time. Previous experiences show that mobile technology can foster a broader and more dynamic involvement of inhabitants than traditional participatory methods (Duarte, Mateus, 2020; Salama, Patil, 2024). In addition, the information collected provides a more accurate and immediate set of data, images and locations, available for consultation and periodic evaluation (UN-Habitat, 2020).

In this sense, this collaborative mapping will help the DISU team to determine priority areas and the types of interventions that can meet the demands of the neighbors. In turn, neighbors find more efficient channels of participation for establishing improvements.

From an academic point of view, these experiential approaches help students understand the complexities of the functionality of urban space and the dynamics of user interaction, with the consequent possibility of developing projects or designing comprehensive strategies based on the real needs of the population, taking advantage of locally rooted knowledge and practices, and co-designing solutions that can be sustainable in the long term.

Environmental, safety, and infrastructure challenges impact public spaces and pedestrian mobility in informal settlements.

Proposal guidelines. Source: Urban Planning Workshop (IA, EHYS, UNSAM, 2024).

Scale 1 in 1. The constructions in true magnitude

In the case of Costa del Lago, the neighbors have been working for some time to build consensus to not occupy the last available land with housing, which is one of the last vestiges of the original wetland, and is therefore susceptible to flooding. At the same time, they also complain about the lack of green spaces, community facilities and infrastructure to clean up the area. At the beginning of 2024 we started to work together with the "Rincón de Esperanza/Cooperativa 9 de Julio community kitchen" one of the neighbors in front of this space and the DISU team.

Together we co-designed a work methodology to reflect on the potential of this space for the community and to define an occupation strategy that would allow not only its use but also a way to "institutionalize" this public space, with the consensus of the municipality. In this sense, the responses are framed in a protocol of listening and joint action established under the following stages:

The development of these projects had a first stage of conversation and public interviews, understood as an exercise of knowledge that attempts an initial approach to the subject and the problems to be solved, as well as to understand the future projections and their limitations. The exercise of collective thinking was materialized in a program of consensual needs, consisting of interpreting everything heard in the conversations with the community and the project's beneficiaries.

The next step was the development of the urban and architectural project of various proposals arising from this agreement and developed by groups of students, with the physical and infrastructure requirements, the possibility of being built in stages, the possible growth, the hypotheses of flexibility and transformation of spaces, and the prefiguration of the maximum dimension of the project.

These processes of conversation, listening and interpretation operate as a design strategy and as a device for the production of trust and affection, fundamental to gain access to the popular knowledge installed in the territory. The technical skill, necessary for the exercise of design, is complemented in these experiences with the exercise of social skill, which places design as a production platform on another plane. By social skill we consider the exploration of a technical plane linked to collaborative formats and stimulus to collective intelligence, reinterpreting the concept of traditional authorship.

The next stage is the consensual selection of the proposal that, in the opinion of the neighbors, complies with the greatest number of slogans and programs built during the collective participation workshops.

Proposal for community facilities. TEP / LET, 2024.

The exercise of listening fosters mutual learning, collective construction, social bonding, and the creation of identities.

The next stage is the project management and construction stage, a new instance that challenges us to continue designing new work methodologies that allow us to listen to all the participating actors.

The extended exercise of listening establishes that the dynamics of the tasks, their improvement, the mutual learning through the exchange of experiences, the overcoming of the difficulties that always inevitably arise, are enriched and form an important part of the project process.

At the same time, an attempt is made to recover an ancestral content linked to the collective act of construction as an event of mystical and inspirational character, which contains an energy of social bonding not easily accessible through other human experiences, through the pursuit of a common goal and the democratization of protagonism and authorship. This sum of challenges extends to aspects of sociological interest, as the reflection on the possibilities of building collective identities through mediating architectures, which could contribute to the integration of communities.

Tour of TEP students, together with the DISU team, neighbors and representatives of the cooperatives. Sharing workshop at Comedor Rincón de Esperanza/Cooperativa 9 de Julio. Nov. 2024.

References

Defensoría del Pueblo de la Nación (2007). Informe especial cuenca del río Reconquista

Duarte, T, Mateus, D. (202). Planning of public open spaces with digital tools. The example of the WAY CyberParks. In Smaniotto Costa, C. et al. (Eds.) Co-Creation of Public Open Spaces. Practice, Reflection, Learning (pp. 243-255) Lisbon: Lusófona University Press.

Giorno, M.y Dadon, J. (2016). Patrones de ocupación informal de la costa del Río Reconquista, Partido de Gral. San Martín. Centro de Investigaciones. Gestión de Espacios Costeros. Facultad de Arquitectura, Diseño y Urbanismo. Universidad de Buenos Aires. Documento de trabajo.

Gutiérrez, A., Pereyra, L., Peláez, E., Scholl, L., Tassara, D. (2022). Movilidad y accesibilidad en asentamientos informales de Buenos Aires: El caso de los barrios de Costa Esperanza, Costa del Lago y 8 de Mayo. Nota técnica IDB-TN-2440. Banco Interamericano de Desarrollo. División de Transporte.

Janches, F., Henderson, H. y MacColman, L. (2014). Riesgo urbano y adaptación al cambio climático en la Cuenca del Río Reconquista. Lincoln Institute of Land Policy. Documento de trabajo.

Mehta, V. (2008). Walkable streets: pedestrian behavior, perceptions and attitudes. Journal of Urbanism: International Research on Placemaking and Urban Sustainability, 1(3), 217-245.

Morandeira, N., Castesana, P., Cardo, M., Salomone, V., Vadell, M., Rubio, A. (2019). An interdisciplinary approach to assess human health risks in an urban environment: a case study in temperate Argentina. Heliyon, 5(10) e02555.

Salama, A., Patil, M. (2024). A mobile application tool for co-assessing urban open spaces - a test case of the Grey's Monument, Newcastle, UK, Journal of Urban Design.

Sutherland, W., Shackelford, G., Christian Rose, D. (2017). Collaborating with Communities: Co-Production or Co-Assessment? Oryx 51 (4): 569-570.

UN-Habitat (2020). City-Wide Public Space Assessment Toolkit- a Guide to Community-Led Digital Inventory and Assessment of Public Spaces. Nairobi, Kenya.

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Community Initiatives of Inclusive Territorial Development in Latin American Cities

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Neighbors of the Vitória / Izidora Occupation in Belo Horizonte discuss the importance of food sovereignty

The last decade was marked by global insurgent movements that occupied public spaces to express dissent and to challenge dominant discourse and practices (Briata et al, 2020). Such gatherings were triggered in many cases, by the struggles of everyday life in the city: repression of uses of the public space, the gentrification of neighbourhoods, the delivery of decent public services or the unaffordability of housing, that soon escalated to wider calls for better democracy and social equality.

Commentators have noted how these movements, despite their inchoate and large spectrum of grievances, constituted incipient political moments for radical systemic change (Dikeç & Swyngedouw, 2017). The challenge was then to sustain the passage from urban social movements to urban political movements, able 'to move from outbursts of indignation to the slow process of sustained transformative strategies through which a new socio-political spatialization becomes imagined, practised, and universalized' (Karaliotas & Swyngedouw, 2019: 378).

The local scale was seen by new political articulations as a 'strategic site for a transformative and prefigurative politics' capable of contesting territories (Russell, 2019: 991). While the aim was to enter institutional spaces and reorganise its structures and distribute power, this was to be coordinated with mobilisations from inside and outside government boundaries with the potential of advancing social rights and developing new forms of governance to counter territorial accumulation (Pradel & García Cabeza, 2018).

Such experiences - including the creation of cooperatives, the remunicipalisation of privatised services and the incubation of social enterprises - were marked by tensions and contestations and required further analysis (Thompson, 2021). Altogether, some of these initiatives came under the umbrella of the global 'new municipalist' movement aimed at forging translocal networks of solidarity and shared practices among urban movements (Silvestre & López Fittipaldi, 2023). Here we examine some of these initiatives in the cities of Rosario (Argentina), Belo Horizonte (Brazil), and Santiago de Chile.

Processes of territorial accumulation in cities

Colonialism has left indelible marks in the constitution of Latin American cities marked by social and spatial segregation, territorial dispossession and the selective and incomplete provision of rights and benefits. Contemporary manifestations of such processes are found in new rounds of displacement of vulnerable groups and the production of exclusive spaces (Janoschka & Sequera, 2016).

Like many other cities, the construction of luxury housing and gated communities in Rosario, Belo Horizonte and Santiago has had the dual process of expelling the urban poor from inner city informal settlements as well as from peri-urban areas, reaping the benefits of increased land values stemming from public investment.

In the northwestern edge of Rosario, the peri-urban neighbourhood of Nuevo Alberdi was historically marked by floods. After the canalisation of streams by the local government in 2007, neighbours of the popular settlement started to be harassed by land speculators while a secretive plan to build a gated community started to be rolled out, prompting the articulation of resistance. In Belo Horizonte, despite successive rounds of progressive local governments that institutionalised the participation of social movement representatives in policy design, the slow delivery of social housing was aggravated by the real estate boom of the mid-2000s and displacement of communities for the hosting of mega-events. New housing movements were formed to break from the impasse in which established ones were trapped in and organise new rounds of occupation of vacated land (Silvestre, 2024).

In Santiago, similar revanchist processes took place in central areas of the city for large projects including residential towers, universities and the gentrification of working class neighbourhoods that led to the formation of new articulations of protest (Casgrain & Janoschka, 2013).

Colonial legacies shape Latin American cities through segregation, displacement, and exclusive developments, prompting resistance against gentrification and real estate speculation.

Maestranza Ukamau social housing was the winner of the Aporte Urbano 2021 award in Santiago, Chile.

Contesting territories

The increased dispossession of the urban poor and territorial accumulation in the three cities heightened contestation leading to the new forms of resistance. The trajectory of autonomist movements in Argentina has a long precedent being born out of the deep economic and social crisis that hit the country following the 2001 recession and riots. After consolidating popular programmes in education, culture and food security in Nuevo Alberdi, the social movement Ciudad Futura (formerly known as Giros) coordinated a campaign in 2010 to resist the displacement of residents.

The *Ya basta!* ('enough!') campaign both denounced the silent evictions taking place and proposed a municipal decree to stop new gated communities in the city that successfully managed council approval.

New housing movements in Belo Horizonte such as Brigadas Populares mobilised the constitutional right of the social function of land to justify the occupation of vacant spaces in the city and provide housing for the poor. Although recognised but rarely enforced, the concept of social function was conceived to counter the speculation of land sitting idle to benefit from an increase in value once surrounding areas are developed and receive public infrastructure.

Over the 2008-2015 period, 55,000 people in more than 14,000 households were settled in land occupations. Following the country-wide protests of 2013, large occupations such as Izidora and Dandara managed to put enough pressure on the local and regional governments for those land being expropriated and recognised as areas eligible for public investment.

Responding to the lack of perspectives of social improvement and the deadlock of neoliberal policies, Chile experienced successive rounds of protests since 2006 and the articulation of new social movements. Among these was Ukamau, formed in popular neighbourhoods of the inner-city district of Santiago Central to struggle for housing.

The group creatively identified and denounced land under public ownership such as railway land that could be repurposed for social housing. Having passed as a fictitious developer to get the official response from the railway company that an area with the size of 3 hectares could be made available, Ukamau organised street protests and occupations of public buildings to gain the commitment for new social housing to be built.

Ciudad Futura activists explain the co-production of a master plan for the Nuevo Alberdi neighborhood of Rosario

Prefiguring new territorial politics

The cases examined here result from a new consciousness that it is not enough to denounce injustices and expect the state to fulfil promises to more distributive policies. Groups like Ciudad Futura, Brigadas Populares and Ukamau mobilised a dual strategy of occupying institutional positions as well as providing concrete evidence that alternative ways of producing, inhabiting and managing territories are possible. The co-design of housing and masterplanning neighbourhoods was a central feature in the struggle for reclaiming and defending popular territories.

As Ciudad Futura developed as a movement party and became the main electoral alternative in Rosario, it also articulated support with the national government for the inclusion of Nuevo Alberdi in a selected group of popular neighbourhoods benefiting from new public infrastructure. A masterplan for the area was developed between residents and supporting architecture and planning professionals to identify the key infrastructure needed. The implementation of water and sanitation infrastructure was prioritised and residents organised themselves to ensure that works followed according to what was planned and that all households were connected and fully functional.

The occupation of Izidora in Belo Horizonte followed a pre-conceived strategy to occupy plots in a vacant area belonging to a developer following the planning guidelines and design defined by the municipality. Supported by volunteers from areas such as urban planning, architecture, engineering, law among others, such strategy helped to ensure integration with the surrounding neighbourhoods and facilitate the future implementation of infrastructure.

[7] "to carry innovative comparative research to document, visualise and mutually connect contested territories, facilitating local-to-global knowledge diffusion of bottom-up models of scientific, cultural, political and economic innovation" (Research Objective 2).
"to advance the state-of-the art in the social sciences and humanities ... questioning how and who generates knowledge on development; challenging the notion of the ownership of scientific knowledge and tools" (Research Objective 3).

The pressure and participation of residents and Brigadas Populares representatives in participatory processes to define a new statutory plan for the city, resulted in the recognition of the area under the label of special zone of social interest, serving to deter the displacement of residents. This was possible due to the work of the movement representatives elected as councillors.

Following the agreement for a new social housing project to be built in Santiago Central, Ukamau mobilised the support of a prestigious architecture practice to co-design a project with more than 400 units. The project Maestranza Ukamau was inaugurated at the end of 2020 following a decision to promote conviviality and proximity among the residents. It won Chile's national architecture prize in 2023 while the project advanced to phase 2 with a new development of another 200 units in a nearby area.

Grassroots movements reclaim territories through political participation, co-designed housing, and infrastructure to resist displacement.

Sharing best practice

The cases examined became important references in the defence and development of popular territories. The social movements and activists supporting them are regularly called upon to share their experience with other movements, academia and the media. However, this creates additional pressure on their limited time and resources. Contested Territories researchers worked alongside the social movements to address this issue through the development of a platform showcasing grassroots best practice, facilitating networks and peer to peer exchanges. Selected practices in the cases discussed here were registered through in-depth interviews with residents and activists to facilitate the dissemination of knowledge.

A documentary film series, executive summaries and reports will be made available in the digital platform Urban Prefigurations due to be launched in early 2025. This collaborative project is being designed for a longevity beyond the timeframe of Contested Territories and will directly⁷contribute to the project's wider research objectives .

References

- Briata, P., Colomb, C., & Mayer, M. (2020). Bridging across differences in contemporary (urban) social movements: territory as a catalyst. *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 8(4), 451-460.
- Casgrain, A., & Janoschka, M. (2013). Gentrification and resilience in Latin American cities: The example of Santiago de Chile. *Andamios*, 10(22), 19-44.
- Dikeç, M., & Swyngedouw, E. (2017). Theorizing the politicizing city. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(1), 1-18.
- Janoschka, M., & Sequera, J. (2016). Gentrification in Latin America: addressing the politics and geographies of displacement. *Urban Geography*, 37(8), 1175-1194.
- Karaliotas, L., & Swyngedouw, E. (2019). Exploring insurgent urban mobilizations: from urban social movements to urban political movements? In *Handbook of Urban Geography*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 369-382.
- Pradel, M. , & García Cabeza, M. G. (Eds.) (2018). *The moment of citizenship: social innovation and urban governance*. Catarata.
- Russell, B. (2019). Beyond the local trap: New municipalism and the rise of the fearless cities. *Antipode*, 51(3), 989-1010.
- Silvestre G. (2024). Participatory planning and the insurgent city: the challenges of the right to the city in Belo Horizonte. In Rocco R; Silvestre G, (eds.) *Insurgent Planning Practice*, pp.155-174. Newcastle upon Tyne: Agenda Publishing.
- Silvestre, G. & Lopez Fittipaldi, M. (2023) *Is there a wave of Latin American municipalism?* Open Democracy. Available at <https://www.opendemocracy.net/es/ola-municipalismo-latinoamericano>
- Thompson, M. (2021a). What's so new about New Municipalism? *Progress in Human Geography*, 45(2), 317-342

Markets and Neighbourhoods against Gentrification: The Experience of the San Fernando Market (Lavapiés, Madrid)

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The neoliberal transformation of urban spaces in order to maximise rent extraction impacts both residential areas (housing) and commercial distribution spaces (trade and markets), ultimately shaping production and consumption patterns. Gentrification and touristification involve territorial accumulation that entail the revaluation (and its associated creative destruction) of commercial spaces and, particularly supply markets and the social practices they sustain.

From this point of view, food markets are a territory in dispute between different modes of commercialisation with a diversity of capitals and agents of different scales (family, community, global) and their corresponding interests, discourses and strategies of action. The transformation of these spaces, although carried out by the silent hand of the market, is not exempt from territorial and discursive conflicts.

The transformation of food markets (and, in general, of all commercial spaces) entails processes of accumulation and territorial dispossession, materializing in disputes among different social groups over territorial use and competing commercial models - such as small traditional commerce, the large-scale commerce of global operators, gentrified/touristified commerce with higher economic profitability (such as gourmet distribution and the hotel and catering trade oriented towards the transient tourist population), cooperative production and commerce, and even self-managed and solidarity-based circuits of proximity production-distribution-consumption.

Neoliberalism reshapes food markets, fueling disputes between traditional, global, and tourist-oriented commerce

The latter may eventually imply the transformation of the market space into an urban commons (cf. Laval and Dardot 2015, p. 155; Hardt & Negri, 2009), a counter-space where alter practices are produced that provide the opportunity to rehearse in the present the relations and practices that one wants to experience in future food spaces.

These different modes of commercialization (and consumption) coexist in tension, competing territorially among various food markets and even within the same market space, as seen in the case of San Fernando Market in the Lavapiés neighborhood of Madrid's Centro district (see Atlas of Territorial Accumulation, 2024), which we analyze here.

As García et al. (2016) point out, the transformation of Madrid's food markets is part of the development plans that aim to insert the city into the global tourist and financial circuit, building an image of a competitive city with international projection. Local markets have become contested spaces, caught between traditional retail shops, large-scale distribution centers, and new gourmet ventures. In the process of gentrification, the former food markets were transformed into hotel, leisure and recreational spaces, similar to shopping centres designed for the local middle classes and passers-by (tourism), weakening and transforming their original social function of supplying fresh food to the city's working classes.

Sequera et al. (2018) show that, in order to justify the conversion process, food markets were stigmatised by local administrations and business sectors as a marketing model in crisis. In these discourses, their loss of competitiveness vis-à-vis global operators (supermarkets, shopping centres and franchises) was attributed to factors such as obsolete commercial practices (due to a lack of adaptation to the needs of an ageing population and to the new shopping habits derived from the extension of salaried work and effective working hours in the young population), deficient personal attention, untidy, dirty and even unhealthy spaces, and the focus of controversial social practices (crime, prostitution, drug trafficking).

[8] These alter practices can expand the frontiers of what is possible and thinkable in current conjunctures (Caffentzis & Federici, 2013; Gutiérrez Aguilar 2017). Alternative practices reflect prefigurative social projects where different social groups rehearse here and now the society that is longed for and fought for (Graeber, 2009, p. 235, 433; Hardt & Negri, 2017, pp. 274-288, 288; Stavrides, 2016, p. 246).

The loss of competitiveness led to the abandonment of jobs and the absence of generational replacement for their retired concessionaires.

Stigmatising narratives framed the need for new investments to 'modernize and update' them. In this way, projects were legitimised to transform the infrastructure and social functions of the markets towards their conversion into spaces for tourist consumption: shops that previously offered basic necessities for the popular environment were displaced by gourmet spaces and, finally, by hotel and catering spaces designed for a middle or upper class transient population. Territorially, the dispute is taking place in the former municipally-owned food markets, mainly in the neighbourhoods of the city's central core.

This process was made possible through the implementation of three successive public policies: between 2003 and 2011 the Innovation and Transformation Plan for the Municipal Markets of Madrid (drawn up by the Madrid City Council in 2003); between 2012 and 2015 the same plan was expanded with an emphasis on marketing and advertising of the Mercados de Madrid brand; finally, in the period 2017-2021 the Strategic Plan for the Municipal Markets of Madrid was implemented, focusing on the physical renovation of the buildings with the financial support of large companies to increase profitability.

The neoliberal transformation of food markets has not been uniform, as it is shaped by the interplay of social and historical contexts, institutional dynamics, and the positioning of different social actors (cf. Peck et al, 2009, p. 53). Depending on these factors, they range from spaces for catering and gourmet food oriented towards the transient population, through spaces that combine traditional food shops with catering, to cases where the market is transformed into a space of urban experimentation that includes alternative social practices to the logic of the neoliberal market.

These include the commercialisation of local agroecological and artisanal production, cooperative distribution, the appropriation of the territory of the market for social and cultural contestatory practices and even experiences of resistance to the neoliberal market such as the Puesto en Construcción-PEC (an interdisciplinary space for the dynamisation of experimental urban and social practices)

and the consumption groups (self-managed circuits that integrate local agroecological production and its distribution in co-responsible and solidarity-based networks of producers and consumers) grouped in the Red Agroecológica de Lavapiés (Agroecological Network of Lavapiés).

It is interesting to note that the Activities Committee of the Market Traders' Association supported the reception of these groups, valuing the benefits they could bring to the market, both for the dynamisation of the space and the complementary purchases that the members of the groups made in traditional commerce. These alternative practices highlight the agency of self-organized consumers in shaping production-commercialisation-consumption circuits.

The Mercado de San Fernando, in the Lavapiés neighbourhood of Madrid, is an example of the complexity of transformation processes and the agency of the local community.

The market is located in Lavapiés, the most multicultural neighbourhood in Madrid's central district (33% of its population is of Moroccan, sub-Saharan, Asian and Latino origin, settled in different migratory waves) and with a long tradition of contested social and cultural movements - including neighbourhood movements for the right to the city, self-managed social centres in occupied spaces (such as the CSOA El Laboratorio) or ceded spaces (such as the CSA Tabacalera), associations and cooperatives of solidarity economy and committed social urbanism).

Since the 1990s, the replacement of the autochthonous population by immigrants has been combined with gentrification processes due to the influx of the bobo population. As Sequera et al. (2016) point out, after the economic crisis of 2008, the market was in decline, with 50% of the stalls empty in 2012. After several unsuccessful attempts to incorporate different supermarket chains on the ground floor, and to house the neighbourhood Health Centre on part of the upper floor, the Traders' Association - in collaboration with the Platform in Defence of the Abastos Markets, which brought together local activist groups related to the right to the city and agroecology - decided to offer the stalls at their real price in local networks in the neighbourhood. This project ensured that, within a year, all the vacant stalls were filled.

This process produced a mixed configuration of the market, adapted to the new population and the alternative culture of the neighbourhood (but not to immigration), which maintains the traditional stalls and combines them with young neighbourhood initiatives and ventures. These initiatives include a wide spectrum of gentrified and alternative commerce: from agro-ecological and local cooperative production to cultural products (such as books by weight) and organic and local food/drink stalls, which were later joined by some stalls with 'ethnic' products and catering run by immigrants.

The central market space regularly hosts cultural events (music, popular dance classes, children's shows) and, for some years, even functioned as a distribution node for various consumer groups (Sequera et al., 20165). While the new traders cater to young, upper-middle class customers, who frequent the market on Fridays and weekends, the traditional food traders continue to serve (older) customers from the neighbourhood on a daily basis (Robles, 2015).

Mercado de San Fernando reflects community agency, resisting gentrification through local networks and solidarity economy

The strong presence of a deep-rooted neighbourhood movement advocating for the right to the city, along with the eruption of the 15M indignados movement in 2011—occupying numerous central public spaces—were key factors in pushing the municipal administration to accept a transformative project distinct from the usual neoliberal model. It is a model that is contemporary with the traditional market and meets the demands of the social movements of resistance to the gentrification of the neighbourhood and its market.

Experience demonstrates that this project is not static; socio-political conditions—such as cycles of mobilization and the strength of social movements — have continually shaped the market's evolution. Since the implementation of the alternative model, the market's structure has been shaped by tensions between this approach and neoliberal pressures to maximize urban rent extraction. The result has been competition and territorial conflict between traditional

(food stalls/ultramartines, conventional agriculture and livestock), alternative (local food products, cultural products and activities aimed at local residents) and neoliberal (gourmet food stalls and catering aimed at the city's middle class and passers-by/tourists) uses and spaces. Over time, operators—both individual entrepreneurs and investment funds—gradually acquired traditional stalls, shifting the balance of power within the Traders' Association and influencing market management, while alternative stalls struggled to remain profitable and eventually exited the market .

The case of the San Fernando market illustrates the complexity and diversity of actors involved in the transformation of food markets amid gentrification and touristification . The analysis of the transformation process allows us to identify internal and external agents that can be systematised into three categories: traditional, neoliberal and counter-hegemonic agents.

Among the internal actors, the most prominent are the traditional stakeholders—owners (assignees) and workers of traditional market stalls—who manage grocery stalls, conventional agriculture, and livestock aimed at supplying the local working-class population . Secondly, neoliberal actors include individual entrepreneurs and investment funds, often supported or facilitated by market management .

These agents promote gourmet food stalls and catering, targeting the city's middle class population and the transient tourist population. Finally, counter-hegemonic actors include new stallholders and workers engaged in gentrified and alternative commerce .

These enterprises are engaged in a wide range of activities, including the sale of local agro-ecological and cooperative production, cultural products, organic and local catering (food/drink), sale of "ethnic" products and catering run by immigrants (Latin American, European), cultural dynamisation (organisation of cultural events, music, popular dance classes, shows, etc.) and the promotion of cultural events (music, popular dance classes, shows, etc.): music, popular dance classes, children's shows, meeting and distribution of consumer groups (self-organised groups of direct relationship between market gardeners and consumers) and the Puesto en Construcción-PEC

(an interdisciplinary space for the dynamisation of experimental urban and social practices).

External actors influencing the market can be categorized similarly: among traditional actors, the local food trade in the surrounding area stands out. The San Fernando Market is immersed in a dense environment of food shops run by both the local population and the different immigrant groups in the neighbourhood, and aimed at supplying the local population (immigrant and local). Secondly, there are also external neoliberal agents, starting with the Municipal Administration (formal owner of the market), as well as global operators of large supermarkets.

These include a Carrefour supermarket open 24 hours a day in the nearby central square of the neighbourhood, and DIA, Lidl and Mercadona shops in the vicinity. This group also includes the neighbourhood's gentrification and tourism agents, which include investment funds and individual owners oriented towards the purchase of homes and their conversion into high-end flats, as well as owners and operators (such as Airbnb) of homes for tourist use, for whom the gourmet market represents part of the symbolic promotional capital for the rental or sale of their properties.

Finally, the neighbourhood's environment is also characterised by the existence of a dense network of counter-hegemonic agents embodied in long-standing and present social protest movements, both urban (for the right to the city) and ecological (food sovereignty and agro-ecology, self-managed consumer groups), socio-cultural (squatted social centres, anti-racist and intercultural groups), which made the neighbourhood one of the focal points of the municipalist political movement. As in all markets, the transformation of San Fernando has been conditioned by the action of this diversity of actors, their alliances (temporary, permanent) and conflicts.

The particularity of this case has been the formation of an apparent balance between the contradictory projects of traditional, neoliberal and counter-hegemonic modes of commercialisation and consumption. The latter field is particularly interesting for its combination of adaptive resistance strategies, which attempt to reconcile capitalist commercial practices with alternative modes of consumption (agro-ecological and proximity food products,

San Fernando Market exemplifies the coexistence of traditional, neoliberal, and counter-hegemonic commerce, highlighting resistance through self-managed, solidarity-based food networks that challenge neoliberal accumulation and preserve food markets' social and community functions amid gentrification.

resident-oriented cultural products and activities) under market conditions and resistance practices that experiment with alternative supply and social relations to the logic of the neoliberal market. In particular, the consumer groups re self-managed circuits that integrate local agroecological production and distribution in co-responsible and solidarity-based networks of producers and consumers that are not governed by the logic of the neoliberal market and prefigure alternative social and production relations to capitalism.

This case shows the conditions of possibility (and the limits) of experiences of resistance to neoliberal territorial accumulation in food markets in the hostile context of gentrification and touristification processes. The case makes visible the agentive potential of self-organised producer and consumer projects in the configuration of alternative solidarity circuits of production-commercialisation-consumption.

These practices shape the food market as a hub for alternative production and social relations, concretely demonstrating that food markets can be organized beyond capitalism, with the construction of the commons at the core of social change (cf. Federicci 2020, p. 31). The experience of the San Fernando market enriches the reflection on the social and political conditions and strategies of action that make it possible to resist the expansion of the neoliberal model and its correlative destruction of other (traditional and alternative) practices of production and commercialisation, eroding the social functions of food markets as spaces for popular provisioning and community structuring.

References

- Atlas of Territorial Accumulation (2024). Markets and neighbourhoods against gentrification. <https://www.contested-territories.net/atlas/mercados-y-barrios-contra-la-gentrificacion/>
- Federicci, S. (2020). *Re-enchanting the world. Feminism and the politics of the commons*. Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños.
- García Pérez, E., Rodríguez Sebastián, A., & Maiello, V. (2016). The transformation of Madrid's municipal markets: new frontiers of commercial gentrification. *Alteridades*, 26(51), 43-56. http://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0188-70172016000100043&lng=es&tlng=es
- Graeber, D. (2009). *Direct Action. An Ethnography*. Oakland, CA: AK Press.
- Gutiérrez Aguilar, R. (2017). *Community-popular horizons. Production of the common beyond state-centric politics*. Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños.
- Hardt, M. & Negri, A. (2009). *Commonwealth*. Cambridge, MA: The Belknap Press.
- Hardt, M, & Negri, A. (2017). *Assembly*. NY: Oxford University Press.
- Laval, C. & Dardot, P. (2015). *Common. Essay on revolution in the 21st century*. Barcelona: Gedisa.
- Peck, J., Theodore, N. & Brenner, N. (2009) Neoliberal urbanism: Models, moments, mutations. *SAIS Review*, 29 (1), 49-66.
- Sequera, J., Cabrerizo, C., & Bachiller, P.. (2018). Inhabited market: Lavapiés market in dispute. In AAVV, "Una Ciudad Muchos Mundos: Investigación artística y prácticas situadas" (pp. 52-65). Madrid: Intermediae (Ayuntamiento de Madrid).
- Stavrides, S. (2016). *Towards the city of thresholds*. Madrid: Akal.

Extractivism in the Canary Islands: The Colonial History of a Territorial Periphery

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In general terms, capital needs commodification in order to be endowed with value and to be able to circulate (Castree 2003). Tourism activity is yet another form of growing commodification of resources to be consumed by those who visit territories, and has become a central piece of neoliberalization. Tourism, through the agents that benefit from it, establishes in the process of commodification a fetishist filtering articulated through appropriations, selections of local cultures and representations (Cheong and Miller 2000), while generating other forms of domination over resident populations in different spheres (job insecurity, access to spaces of social reproduction, etc.).

Thus, from governments, private companies and international organizations, strong impulse has been given to this activity, favoring the concentration of capital located in wealthy countries (Büscher and Fletcher 2017). Its recent expansion coincides with the orientation towards a more flexible model aimed at new visitor preferences such as ecotourism (Fletcher 2019), luxury tourism (Fletcher 2016), or 'accommodation mimicry' with local residents (Armas-Díaz 2023).

Environmental conflicts are the first to emerge in more advanced stages of the installation of tourism activity in the Canary Islands (Armas et al. 2020). In the first stage (1960-1973), this activity coexisted with other activities such as agriculture and fishing without generating major conflicts; it was concentrated in a few places but intensely. The second tourism boom (1985-1989), closely linked to a phase of accelerated international capital flows, had a very broad territorial impact despite its short duration, during which the land developed for tourism doubled (Martín 2000), and the demand for water (to the detriment of agricultural irrigation), energy consumption and waste generation multiplied. Between 1997 and 2006, Spain witnessed a housing boom, exceptional in its intensity and duration, and especially intense in large cities and tourist areas such as the Canary Islands (WMO 2013).

Unlike the previous stage, this accumulation cycle affected most of the urban island territory, and was not limited to the increase in tourist supply. It also extended to regular housing, second homes, apartments and luxury villas for foreign seasonal residents, as well as intense infrastructure development and megaprojects.

Contradictions were produced, such as the regulation of hotel vacancies *ex novo*, allowing the manufacture of only those with superior category. Something that has continuity, in particular with the development of new ways of tourism - e.g. forms of green-label tourism - green arguments in its concreteness and the use of less transformed nature, which again plays a fundamental role in the expansion and accumulation of capital (Fletcher 2019).

The most widespread form of territorial accumulation in the Canary Islands is tourist exploitation since the 1960s. Although it is an implantation that takes place at a recent moment in history, it gives continuity to a colonial project initiated at the end of the 15th century on the way to the invasion of America, with the colonization and conquest of the Atlantic archipelagos (Moore 2017). At that time, a progressive capitalization of land ownership and specialized agricultural production began, but in cycles (sugar cane, cochineal, vineyards, bananas, tomatoes, etc.) and concentrated in a few hands, as well as its export controlled by foreign powers to Europe (Sabaté Bel 2008).

The trend for centuries in the Canary archipelago was different from that of the European continent, where a progressive process of industrialization took place, until the fascist regime of Franco imposed a new agenda based on tourism in different territories, the archipelagos of the Canary and Balearic Islands, as well as part of the Spanish coast became the main tourist areas of the planet (Murray 2015).

*Touristification by airbnbification in the rural protected area of El Rincón.
Author: Alejandro Armas Díaz*

The tourism-development binomial was embraced by authoritarian regimes (Bianchi and Stephenson 2018) and imposed by the agenda of international organizations especially in peripheral and insular regions as a strategy of accumulation (Scheyvens 2024).

Tourism and real estate replaced agriculture, sparking environmental protests and continuous citizen mobilizations

Thus, real estate specialization and tourism emerged from the mid-twentieth century as the two fundamental forms of territorial accumulation in the Canary Islands, relegating that based on agricultural production, while at the same time transferring the surpluses towards a new cycle of accumulation in which foreign capital acquired even greater relevance and in which the construction of large infrastructures -ports, roads, airports, etc.- would be notable (García Herrera 1987, Armas-Díaz and Sabaté Bel 2022).

In sum, and with some differences, island production -urban primacy, self-construction, dependence, tourism, etc.- shares the characteristics of island countries and territories in peripheral and developing situations (García Herrera 1987). During the second stage of the expansion of tourist activity on the islands, the protest was marked by innumerable confrontations driven by local groups. They fought against the impacts generated by tourism and real estate projects in very specific areas, with platforms that defended the preservation of these areas.

At that time, the protest was accompanied by scientific reports, which, coinciding with a progressive majority in parliament, achieved the inclusion of some of these environments and many others through the approval of a Law of Protected Natural Spaces (1987).

In the third of the tourist boom stages (1993-2007), coinciding with the rise of the insular liberal-conservative political regime (Brito 2018), in which the government was characterized by putting up barriers to citizen participation, the growing social indignation was channeled through extra-institutional actions, such as environmentalist protest (Brito 2020, 92), or popular legislative initiatives. The succession of mobilizations led to the normalization of this type of protest which, around 2004-2005, reached an almost permanent character of conflict (ibid.). In particular, environmental mobilizations in the Canary Islands attracted more people than all those focused on social issues (health, education, housing, etc.) (Armas-Díaz and Sabaté-Bel 2024).

Although in the immediate aftermath of the 2008 crisis -due to the context of job insecurity and unemployment- these lost momentum, with exceptions such as the Port of Granadilla (see Armas-Díaz and Sabaté-Bel 2022). However, the social responses that then resurface continue to question and erode neoliberal hegemony. The experience gained is transformed into political capital, generating opportunities for the collective construction of alternative and radical objectives. In those decades, the recurrent mobilization against the destruction of nature vertebrated and reinforced the protest in the Canary Islands (Brito 2018).

The last phase of the process was marked by massive demonstrations in the eight islands of the archipelago against touristification and in favor of limits to growth, in April and October 2024. The broad confluence promoting the mobilizations has initiated the participatory construction of a program (Canarias tiene un límite) that points towards degrowth in a post-capitalist perspective with an eco-social agenda, as is also the case in other touristified archipelagos (Blázquez-Salom et al. 2024).

In synthesis, the various legal actions, demonstrations, creation of participatory and alternative documents, have been enriching the forms of protest in recent decades. The more coordinated intervention of a regional nature defines this new stage, in a skilful deployment of the politics of scale, in which local platforms are called upon when it is a question of illustrating processes of dispossession that are singular and well present in these specific spaces.

Slogan "Construye un hotel destruye un paraíso" (English: Build a hotel destroy a paradise) of the site's fence against the construction of a green labeled and luxury hotel at La Tejita Beach (Tenerife). Author: Alejandro Armas Díaz

Unlike other peripheral or semi-peripheral tourist regions, the Canary Islands archipelago has particular relations in the production of its territoriality: colonial and dependent, due to its economic and political adscription, as well as its geographical position and its archipelagic condition (Armas-Díaz et al. 2024).

Islands are very well defined spaces in material terms, in which borders are a basic element (but not the only ones) in territorial delimitation, but also in practice (Gillis 2004, 114). In other words, territoriality constitutes an essential force in capitalism, which is materialized through state policies that drive hegemonic economic processes and that often end up determining the functions and dependencies of these spaces (Harvey 2003). At the same time, these forms of territorialization take a particular form that relies on the extended relationship between the island and the continent, through which it is "presupposed that the continent is actually the main land, that from which and in relation to which the insular existence is defined, which thus appears in a role if not dominated, at least subordinated and dependent" (Ríos and Hernández Armas 2024, 10).

In the Canary Islands, this has manifested itself in different phases of super-specialization oriented to the exterior, either through export agriculture or tourism. At the same time, the hegemonic narrative of the ultraperiphery from Europe itself and island elites strives to "detach the Canary Islands from dark Africa and link it as far as possible to a luminous Mediterranean" (Pérez Flores 2018, 17).

Thus, the archipelago is placed on the European periphery, and distanced from its historical relationship and the colonial project linked to the European expansion to the African and American continents. While on a global scale the semi-peripheral islands of global capitalism assume subordinate functions, such as tourism, agricultural production and its export, extraction of mineral resources, and many others (Pons et al. 2014).

Similarly, tourism incorporates and reinforces the exotic, selective and exclusive component oriented to those who move to consume it (Estévez Hernández 2021).

Protests evolved with regional coordination, highlighting the Canary Islands' colonial dependency and unique territorial dynamics

It acts, therefore, as "an ideological way of framing history, nature and tradition [...] with the power to reconfigure culture and nature according to its own needs" (Ojeda 2019). In the case of the Canary Islands, tourism is so far the last great project of post-colonial territorialization - rare earth mining could be presented in the medium term as another of them in some of the islands of the Canary archipelago - and which make it more than an economic sector (Estévez Hernández 2021).

However, insularity also plays an essential role, not only because of its capacity to territorialize projects, but also because it is capable of producing a powerful political scale for the collective dispute over resources and against concrete hegemonic projects (Sabaté-Bel and Armas-Díaz 2022). In the words of Lopes de Souza (1995), territories are fields of forces where social groups can project and impose specific territorialities that are linked to their way of life, the maintenance of vital resources and certain identities linked to the freedom to act.

These can take on special relevance in an insular context of reduced dimensions, due to the particular relations with non-human nature, while at the same time circumscribing the singular colonial relations and dependence of the hegemonic territorialities of the archipelago. While nature plays a fundamental role in the accumulation of capital (Smith 2007), it is no less true that the struggle to avoid its destruction and deterioration constitutes a powerful source of opposition and an inspiration for future alternatives (Heynen et al. 2007). Empirical evidence shows that communities in island territories present particularities (Baldacchino 2004). We are interested in highlighting how they display greater awareness of limits than those of continental spaces (Armas-Díaz et al. 2024).

References

- Armas-Díaz, Alejandro; Murray, Ivan; Sabaté-Bel, Fernando & Blázquez-Salom, Macià (2024). Environmental struggles and insularity: The right to nature in Mallorca and Tenerife. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 42(4): 639-657. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>
- Armas-Díaz, Alejandro & Sabaté-Bel, Fernando (2024). Green and Grey Hoarding in the Construction of Infrastructures in Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain). *ACME - An International Journal of Critical Geographies*, 23 (5): 356-378. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>
- Armas-Díaz, Alejandro (2023). How much of the collaborative economy is left: An analysis of non-professional Airbnb hosts in Leipzig (Germany). *Documents d'anàlisi geogràfica*, 69(1): 5-29. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/dag.727>
- Armas-Díaz, Alejandro & Sabaté-Bel, Fernando (2022). Struggles on the port of Granadilla: defending the right to nature. *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 10(2): 256-276. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>
- Armas-Díaz, Alejandro, Sabaté-Bel, Fernando; Murray, Ivan & Blázquez-Salom, Macià (2020). Beyond the right to the island. *Erdkunde*, 74(4): 249-262. <https://doi.org/10.3112/erdkunde.2020.04.02>
- Baldacchino, Godfrey (2004). The coming of age of island studies. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, 95(3): 272-283. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9663.2004.00307.x>
- Blázquez-Salom, Macià; Cañada, Ernest; Müller, Nora & Ramis Sastre, Margalida (2024). Ecologisme i turisticació. From the defense of the territory to the ecosocial transformation. *Compàs d'amalgama*, 9: 32-38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>
- Bianchi, Raoul V. & Stephenson, Marcus L. (2018). Tourism, border politics, and the fault lines of mobility. In Paasi, Anssi; Prokkola, Eeva-Kaisa; Saarinen, Jarkko & Zimmerbauer, Kaj (Eds.). *Borderless Worlds for Whom? Ethic, Moralities and Mobilities* (pp. 121-138), Routledge.
- Brto, Juan M. (2020): The political impact of the environmentalist contest in Tenerife. In Brto, Juan M. (Ed.): *Memoria colectiva y cambio social* (pp. 79-100). Madrid: Los libros de la catarata.
- Brto, Juan M. (2018). Dynamics of Canarian social movements in the cycle of change. In Brito, Juan M. (Ed.). *La acción colectiva en el cambio de época* (pp. 52-90). Madrid: Los libros de la catarata.
- Büscher, Bram & Fletcher, Robert (2017). Destructive creation. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(5): 651-667. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>
- Castree, Noel (2003). Commodifying what nature? *Progress in human geography*, 27(3): 273-297. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0309132503ph428oa>
- Cheong, So-Min & Miller, Marc L. (2000). Power and tourism: A Foucauldian observation. *Annals of tourism research*, 27(2): 371-390. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(99\)00000-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(99)00000-0)
- Estévez Hernández, Pablo (2021). Tourism is war by other means. The biopolitics and geopolitics of the Canary Islands destination. *Atlántida Magazine*, 12: 81-100. <https://doi.org/10.25145/j.atlantid.2021.12.05>
- Fletcher, Robert (2019). Neoliberalism and tourism. In Ernest Cañada & Ivan Murray (Ed.) *Global touristification. Critical perspectives on tourism* (pp. 37-52). Barcelona: Icaria.
- Fletcher, Robert (2016). Cannibal tours brought up to date. *Political Ecology*, 52: 26-34. https://www.ecologiapolitica.info/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/052_Fletcher_2016.pdf
- García Herrera, Luz Marina (1987). Economic Development and Spatial Configuration in the Canary Islands: The role of cities in a peripheral and dependent area. *Antipode*, 19(1): 25-39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1773918>

- Gillis, John R. (2004). *Islands of the mind. How the human imagination created the Atlantic world*. Palgrave Macmillan: New York.
- Harvey, David (2003). *The new imperialism*. Oxford University Press: Oxford.
- Heynen, Nik; McCarthy, James; Prudham, Scott & Robbins, Paul (2007). *Neoliberal environments. False promises and unnatural consequences*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Lopes de Souza, Marcelo J. (1995). O territorio: sobre espacio e poder, autonomía e desenvolvimento. In I. E. de Castro, P. C. da Costa Gomes and R. Lobato Corrêa, (Orgs.). *Geografia: conceitos e temas* (pp. 78-116). Bertrand.
- Martín, Víctor O. (2000). *Tourism in the South of Tenerife*. Cabildo de Gran Canaria. Las Palmas.
- Moore, Jason. W. (2017). The Capitalocene Part II: accumulation by appropriation and the centrality of unpaid work/energy. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 45(2): 237-279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067648.2017.1345444>
- Murray, Ivan (2015). *Capitalism and tourism in Spain. From the "economic miracle" to the "great crisis"*. Barcelona: AlbaSud.
- WMO - Metropolitan Observatory of Madrid (2013). *Devastated landscapes. After the real estate cycle: Urban and regional impacts of the crisis*. Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños.
- Ojeda, Diana (2019). The empty beach, the lush forest and the exotic other: tools for the critical analysis of nature tourism. In Ernest Cañada & Ivan Murray (Ed.) *Global touristification. Critical perspectives on tourism* (pp. 463-474). Barcelona: Icaria.
- Pérez Flores, Larisa (2018). Islands, migration and creolization: the Canary Islands from a decolonial approach. *Anuario de Estudios Atlánticos*, 65, 065-021: 1-19. <http://anuariosatlanticos.casadecolon.com/index.php/aea/article/view/10268>
- Pons, Antoni, Rullan, Onofre and Murray, Ivan (2014). Tourism capitalism and island urbanization: tourist accommodation diffusion in the Balearics, 1936-2010. *Island Studies Journal*, 9(2): 239-258. .
- Ríos, Félix J. and Hernández Armas, Ramón (2024). Insular identities, singular identities. *Revista Atlántida*, 15: 9-12. <https://doi.org/10.25145/j.atlantid.2024.15.01>
- Sabaté-Bel, Fernando & Armas-Díaz, Alejandro (2022). Commodification or the Right to the Island: The Struggle Against the Construction of a Hotel in La Tejita (Tenerife). *Island Studies Journal*, 17(2), 214-234. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15447189.2022.2088888>
- Sabaté Bel, Fernando (2008). El territorio rural como encuentro entre la naturaleza y la cultura humana: Reflexiones sobre su construcción histórica y su crisis contemporánea. *Rincones del Atlántico*, 5, 80-129. https://www.rinconesdelatlantico.es/num5/3_fernando.html
- Scheyvens, Regina (2024). International development and tourism geographies. *Tourism Geographies*, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2024.2330579>
- Smith, Neil (2007). Nature as an accumulation strategy. *Socialist Register*, 43: 16-36. <https://socialistregister.org/issue/43/16-36>

Disputed Territories: Tenants Organised against Capitalist Accumulation

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Securing access to safe and adequate housing is among the most pressing challenges in contemporary societies, particularly in expanding rental markets with minimal tenant protections. In this context, the tenant survey emerges as a key tool that not only documents the structural inequalities of the rental market, but also drives contestation practices organised by social movements globally.

Soaring rents and weak regulatory protections have forcibly displaced thousands of tenants, pushing them into precarious living conditions or forcing them to abandon their communities. According to recent data, rent prices have risen disproportionately over the last two decades, particularly in large cities such as Buenos Aires, Madrid, Barcelona and Lisbon, where tenants spend more than 40% of their income on housing.

This problem disproportionately affects young people and migrants, who face additional barriers due to their economic and social precariousness. The lack of a legal framework that balances contractual relations between landlords and tenants has entrenched a dynamic in which landlords accumulate power and wealth, while tenants suffer the consequences of a system designed to benefit renters.

Territorial accumulation in this context stems from the concentration of properties in the hands of large landlords and investment funds, who leverage their market power to extract rents from tenants. This phenomenon is particularly evident in the cities most affected by real estate speculation, where land liberalisation policies and the withdrawal of housing rights over the last decades have exacerbated property inequalities (Rolnik, 2019).

Legislation favoring landlords has established a framework that permits exorbitant rent hikes and forced evictions, leaving tenants vulnerable to housing insecurity and displacement. According to Harvey (2003), this process of accumulation by dispossession involves not only economic extraction, but also the expulsion of entire communities, entrenching the wealth gap between those who own property and those who depend on the rental market.

This conflict traces its roots to the economic crisis of 2001 in Argentina and 2008 in Spain and Portugal. In both cases, the collapse of mortgage markets marked a turning point in housing dynamics, shifting the problem of access to ownership to the rental market.

In Spain, the 2008 financial crisis triggered a surge in mortgage evictions, pushing many families into the rental market. This transition occurred in a context of increasing financialisation, where neoliberal policies promoted speculation in the rental market (Aalbers, 2016).

Tenant protections were systematically dismantled through legal reforms from the 1970s to the 1990s, eroding key safeguards and consolidating a market overwhelmingly skewed in favor of landlords. This pattern is replicated in many cities in Europe and Latin America, where rental housing has gone from being a transitory stage in people's lives to a permanent condition for large sectors of the population (IDRA, 2024).

In response to this crisis, social movements and tenants' unions have emerged that seek to transform the power dynamics in the rental market. Since 2017, organisations such as the Sindicato de Inquilinas in Spain, HABITA in Portugal or Inquilinos Agrupados in Argentina have successfully amplified the housing crisis, mobilizing thousands of tenants through advocacy campaigns and direct actions.

In Buenos Aires, the survey results were key in fuelling parliamentary debates on rent regulation, while in Barcelona and Madrid, the data strengthened mass mobilisations for the right to housing in the autumn of 2024. These cases illustrate how a tool for situated knowledge production can serve as a political instrument to contest the dominance of the rentier model.

The tenant survey not only makes structural inequalities visible, but also reconfigures power relations in the territory by empowering organised communities. According to Lefebvre (1991), space is not only a stage where social relations occur, but a product of these relations, shaped by power and resistance.

In this sense, the production of autonomous knowledge through the survey is a way of reconfiguring power relations in the territory, strengthening a counter-power capable of delegitimizing the rentier model and proposing alternatives that prioritise universal access to decent housing. In Buenos Aires, the survey results were key in fuelling parliamentary debates on rent regulation, while in Barcelona and Madrid, the data strengthened mass mobilisations for the right to housing in the autumn of 2024. These cases illustrate how a tool for situated knowledge production can serve as a political instrument to contest the dominance of the rentier model.

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By making structural inequalities visible and proposing legislative alternatives, this project contributes to the construction of a fairer and more equitable housing model. However, its success depends on the capacity of social movements to consolidate alliances and pressure governments to prioritise the right to housing over market interests.

"Tenant Survey team associated with Contested Territories surveying in the city of Madrid, Spain."

"Tenant Survey team associated with Contested Territories surveying in the city of Madrid, Spain."

Legal reforms favor landlords, fueling housing insecurity. Tenant movements use surveys to contest the rentier model's dominance

The fight for equitable and secure housing transcends national borders, unfolding in major cities across Europe and Latin America. Territorial accumulation, facilitated by neoliberal policies, has consolidated a patrimonial gap that perpetuates inequality and housing insecurity. However, the contestation practices developed by tenants' movements offer hope for change, demonstrating that it is possible to challenge existing power dynamics and build a future where housing is a right and not a commodity.

The reach of the survey has transcended borders, fostering the building of transnational solidarity networks between tenants' movements. These connections have enabled the sharing of learning, such as the use of the survey to document practices of territorial accumulation in the cities most affected by financialisation. In the framework of Contested Territories, the survey is positioned as a central resource for mapping and denouncing global inequalities in access to housing, consolidating a common discourse between Europe and Latin America.

References

Aalbers, M. B. (2016) *The Financialization of Housing: A Political Economy Approach*. Routledge

Harvey, D. (2005) *The New Imperialism*. Oxford University Press.

IDRA (2023) *Generation Tenant: The Great Social Divide*,

IDRA (2024) *From Landlords to Tenants: The Growing Inequality of Access to Property*,

Lefebvre, H. (1991) *The Production of Space*. Wiley-Blackwell.

Rolnik, R. (2019) *Urban Warfare: Housing Under the Empire of Finance*. Verso Books.

An aerial photograph of a dry, hilly landscape. The terrain is brown and sparsely vegetated with small trees and shrubs. A winding road curves through the hills. In the lower center, there is a small, white, rectangular building. The sky is a clear, dark blue.

 contested
TERRITORIES